

PHOENIX

The Rise of Citizens Voices
for a Greener Europe

Participation in **H**olistic **E**nvironmental/Ecological **I**nnovations

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PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programmed participants (including the commission services)

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Executive summary

The PHOENIX project aims to enrich Democratic Innovations supporting the European Green Deal transition through place-based co-design as a guiding principle. The project employs Territorial Commissions for Co-Design (TCCDs) as platforms for citizens and stakeholders to collaborate in co-designing participatory processes tailored to their local contexts. PHOENIX proposes a tangram approach to assemble different participatory modules into coherent processes, along with technological devices and tools developed by the project.

This deliverable serves as an Information Package to enable each implementer to create a customised briefing for their TCCD. It provides modular components that partners can extract and adapt. The contents cover:

- Concise presentation of the six democratic challenges for the European Green Deal.
- Principles of co-design in democratic innovations and practical guide to organising a TCCD.
- Overviews of the 11 PHOENIX pilots and proposed tangram combinations of participatory modules.
- Descriptions of 6 tools developed by PHOENIX.
- Evaluation plan for assessing TCCD activities and draft of pilot evaluation plan, including pre- and post- survey questionnaires.

The deliverable employs two writing styles - one simplified external style for TCCD members, and one retaining internal project references for partners. Sections on co-design principles, pilots and TCCD activities can be directly extracted and adapted into TCCD Information Packages translated locally.

Overall, this deliverable provides implementers the building blocks to create place-based Information Packages for the TCCD they are organising, supporting context-specific co-design. By compiling PHOENIX principles, findings and tools, it enables partners to extract relevant components, translate and recombine them with local knowledge into responsive briefing materials for their TCCDs. The aim is to foster informed citizen participation and empower TCCDs to enrich Democratic Innovations.

Introduction

The PHOENIX project firmly embraces place-based **co-design** as a guiding principle in its pursuit of **enriching Democratic Innovations** supporting the **European Green Deal** transition pathway. Recognising that participatory processes need to be context-sensitive and responsive to local needs, the project employs the **Territorial Commissions for Co-Design (TCCDs)** and supports them through its tangram approach, tools, and technological devices it developed. These commissions serve as platforms where citizens and stakeholders collaborate, exchange ideas, and collectively co-design the participatory process in their respective territories (pilots of the project).

This Deliverable is designed to provide **key building blocks to enable each implementer to create the Information Package for the TCCD they are implementing**. As such, it is conceived as a modular document comprising sections that can be easily extracted and re-combined. To achieve this purpose, the deliverable includes various sections that offer a comprehensive overview of the principles, methodology, tools, and tangrams proposed for the pilot territories developed and/or empowered by the PHOENIX project.

The contents of the deliverable cover the following issues related to the PHOENIX project:

- The six democratic challenges for the **European Green Deal**.
- The **co-design** principles and methodology: from theory to practice.
- An **overview of the entire project**, democratising its findings, purposes and means.
- The **tools and methods** developed by the project, promoting their spreading in the TCCD territories, and offering the consortium support in their adaptation and implementation.
- The mapping of the **11 pilots** of the project, promoting the cross-fertilisation between the **11 tangrams** proposed to the TCCDs.

To compile these contents, the Information Package has been developed as a systematic, simplified, and summarised version of the project results, deliverables, and internal documents produced thus far by the PHOENIX project (especially Deliverable 3.1 - *Design of Democratic Innovations for Democratic Challenges*, Deliverable 3.2 *Methodologies for Democratic Innovations in Pilot context*, Deliverable 3.3 *Tangram Portfolio – Part 3 Tools for the Tangram*, Deliverable 5.2 - *Draft evaluation plan*, and internal documents of Task 4.1 Territorial Commission for Co-Design and Task 5.2 Participatory testing, localisation and optimisation of the evaluation plan).

There are **three key (direct and indirect) audiences** for this deliverable:

- A) The **TCCD implementer partners**. For them, the deliverable acts as an overall set of building blocks they need to reorganise and combine with their local knowledge and local information to create the briefing package.
- B) The **TCCD members** (through each **TCCD place-based Information Package**).
- C) The **general public** (through our **website**).

Therefore, while we refer to this deliverable as the Information Package for the TCCDs, it is important to understand that **this deliverable is an intermediate step towards the creation of place-based information packages for each TCCD. Thus, no TCCD will be exposed to this deliverable in the current format.** Instead, each partner will extract and adapt the sections of these deliverables that are appropriate for their TCCD and generate **a more agile booklet enriched by place-based information**, which will also be translated in the **local language**.

Due to the presence of multiple audiences, the deliverable maintains two styles. For the ease of navigation for partners that need to use/reorganise the deliverable and create final place-based Information Packages, this document retains internal sign-posting and internal jargon, such as deliverable numbers, in the organising sections and in the indexes (**style I: internal**). While, within each policy brief, we removed as much jargon as possible, avoiding the use of language that might be unfamiliar to the TCCD members and the general public (**style II: external**). We have colour-coded the styles, using **blue** for style I and **black** for style II.

Instructions for TCCD implementers and deliverable map

This document is designed to contain information to assist local partners in creating the TCCD place-based Information Package. We expect the implementers to **customise, integrate, translate into the local language, and then share it with the TCCD members** to support informed participation. Therefore, please note that this document is not meant to be shared with TCCD members as it is; but only after its sections have been selected (and adapted) and translated.

The place-based Information Package should be a concise and agile booklet that contains information that is relevant and operational for each TCCD. As explained in the introduction, the deliverable is written in two different styles, which are colour-coded: in **blue** you will find **instructions for the implementers (Style I) and more complex information with jargon, signposting, references, which is not intended to be included in the TCCD Information Package.** In **black** (style II), you will find **assets that have been carefully curated to be ready to be translated and disseminated among members of the TCCDs.** To make them ready for immediate use after translation, we have removed all references, jargon, mentions to deliverables, and internal signposting from these sections.

This document also includes the most updated guide on the activities to be conducted during the TCCDs, developed by CES and Res publica in conversation with all the members of WP4 in the spring of 2023. During the summer and fall of 2023, WP4 will focus on supporting each local partner in the implementation of their TCCD.

The deliverable is divided into four sections:

- 1. Co-Designing a greener Europe (organising a TCCD)**
- 2. PHOENIX pilot tangrams**
- 3. PHOENIX toolkit**
- 4. Co-Evaluation plan: TCCDs and Pilots.**

The information contained in this deliverable in Section 2 and 3 (and partially in section 1) is derived from the work conducted by other partners during the first two years of the project. It contains the core ingredients to create each place-based TCCD Information Package.

The team at Southampton University (SOTON) has summarised and reorganised the information with the help of the Public Policy unit of SOTON, specialised in knowledge exchange. Dora Vrkic, a senior policy consultant of the Public Policy unit, was invaluable in reviewing, summarising, and adapting the language of all academic deliverables submitted in June, in collaboration with the SOTON project team.

In collaboration with Sofia Francescutto of Fondazione Feltrinelli, we planned the assets of Section 2 and 3 to be built with a user journey in mind for the PHOENIX website (and other local websites). The section of the **PHOENIX website** regarding tools and pilots will have 3 levels of depth for each asset: 1) a short summary of 300 words + an image, 2) a policy brief of 1500 words contained in this deliverable, and 3) the original document derived from the deliverable that elaborates on each asset. This allows us to cater to different types of audiences, from the casual citizen or a journalist seeking a brief overview, to policy makers and journalists interested in a more detailed policy brief, and finally academics and practitioners interested in a fully detailed analysis.

In detail, we have opened Section 1 with an adaptation of the **brief article of Cordier and Syntomer** derived from Deliverable 3.1. This article is more academic in nature and serves as an overall recap of the PHOENIX project objectives. It is not intended for most TCCD members' consumption.

It is the only section in which we have retained complex language and references, and for this reason, we categorise it as **style I**. This article is meant as a knowledge transfer mechanism for all the partners and as an asset for journalists, policy makers, and practitioners that can be used on the website or in media reports.

Section 1.2 regarding the **organisation of TCCDs**, and Section 4, regarding the **evaluation of TCCDs and pilots**, are original content of this deliverable. Section 1.2 contains a brief introduction on codesign created by SOTON and the results of an internal codesign process led by Res publica during the first semester of 2023, which generated a guide on how to implement a TCCD. The codesign section is written in **style II** because we thought the implementers might want to share it with some TCCD members, while the other sections are in **style I** because they are for internal co-design purposes.

Section 4 contains an update of the **overall evaluation plan**. Section 4.1 showcases the **co-evaluation protocol for the TCCD activity**, which was finalised in June 2023 as a result of an internal co-design process led by the University of Coimbra. Section 4.2 introduces the draft evaluation plan for the pilots of Enriched Democratic Innovation. This last section marks the beginning of a co-design process aimed at ensuring that the final evaluation framework (due in January 2024) achieves all the internal objectives established in the Grant while enriching the evaluation approach with locally designed objectives from partners and TCCD. Therefore, each partner and each TCCD will have a dedicated session to expand the **core pre/post-survey system** with an extra dedicated battery of questions that might target locally meaningful Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The **Annex I** provides an example of a possible index for the place-based briefing package that the local partners are required to create and translate.

1. CO-DESIGNING A GREENER EUROPE

1.1 Theoretical framework: the six democratic challenges for the EGD¹

The original PHOENIX proposal identified six crucial challenges that democratic innovation for the **European Green Deal (EGD)** face, each corresponding to critical knots and specific questions grouped in two main domains: the organisational architecture of democratic innovation on the one hand, and the communication among actors and the negotiations among their expectation and interests for improved cooperation on the other hand.

The preparatory work that PHOENIX conducted during the first year of the project applied a systemic approach to the transformative potential of democratic innovations in the context of the European Green Deal (EGD). It focuses primarily on the potential of the most used Democratic Innovations, such as Participatory Budgeting, Citizens' Assemblies, Public Debate and mixed councils and assemblies. Seventy case studies of democratic innovations were analysed and have become part of the library of case studies that each TCCD will be able to access in order to reflect on the variety of approaches to democratic innovations. This library will be made available on our website. The theoretical work conducted by PHOENIX, highlighted **six key challenges from an updated systemic perspective and in relation to the EGD**, aiming to move beyond internalist perspectives on deliberation and consider **fully integrating democratic innovations into the European public space and the Green Deal framework**².

One of the major difficulties of our contemporary democracies in the face of climate change lies in their **short-termist nature**, induced by electoral time, which can lead to a lack of response to more global and slow issues. This form of democratic myopia, as Smith and Curato (2022) express it, poses a real problem, not only for Europe but also for the very existence of human life and ecosystems, since it can prevent our societies from constructing policies whose consequences will only be visible in decades, or even centuries. Another important element, more related to the constitution of democratic innovations to answer to climate change challenges, is found in the tension, recognized by Habermas and Dryzek in particular (see Habermas, 1996; Dryzek, 2012), **between democratic deliberation and decision-making**. As Graham Smith writes, referring to Jane Mansbridge, the fact of making decision means ending at some point the openness and ongoing nature of deliberation (Mansbridge, 1996; Smith, 2009), yet one of the major and persistent concerns in the implementation of deliberative tools remains its connection to the standard political sphere and to decision-making, beyond their consultative role of simple recommendation.

¹ By Lionel Cordier and Yves Sintomer.

² Please refer to Deliverable 3.1 for a detailed analysis.

Therefore, it is not enough to design democratic innovations, it is also necessary to consider their future relationship with pre-existing institutions, and how it will be possible to adapt the framework of the classical political arena to these new expressions.

These two aspects highly connected to climate change policies show the urgent need for a systemic approach to deliberation in relation to environmental protection. This approach points out the need to abandon the centrality of a single model promoting an exclusive space for the development of deliberation and participation. They seek to include a greater number of arenas (spheres), where deliberative and participatory practices can be developed, to observe the presence and distribution of democratic virtues in different spheres that can interact with and diversify the modes of action within these systems. Mansbridge, Parkinson et al. (2012) identify the idea of a system as “a set of distinguishable, differentiable and in a certain sense, interdependent parts, frequently with distributed functions and division of tasks, connected in such a way that they form a whole” (ibid. 6). Likewise, they point out three functions of said system: epistemic (referring to the development of options and decisions), ethical (focused on the relationships between actors) and democratic (valuing the inclusion of actors and the diversity of forms of action).

In line with Jane Mansbridge's observations on the need of systemic approaches, **the PHOENIX project is designed to promote reflection on how produce a genuine European deliberative system in the context of the European Green Deal (EGD).** Launched in 2019, the EGD is a set of policy initiatives aimed at achieving climate neutrality for the European Union by 2050, but which also includes policies for biodiversity and its restoration. It involves considerable funding and a wide variety of policies dealing with energy, food, mobility, and circular economy. With over 500 billion euros of investment, which could rise to nearly one trillion euros including private funding, the EGD has emerged as one of the most crucial and ambitious European programs of the next years, as well as the challenge of becoming a leading ecological power alongside China and the U.S. But as Diogo Guedes Vidal and Maria de Fátima Alves pointed out in Deliverable 2.1 (2023: 63), the ecological transition led by the EGD does not mean greening our current socio-economic systems. It implies much more: a profound transformation of the ways we live, work, and produce. This particularly deep and historic political transformation forces us to imagine and adopt new models of political participation. The fight against climate change cannot come at the expense of social justice and equality. It is necessary to integrate a dimension of justice into European environmental policies, taking into account existing inequalities and potential impacts on the most vulnerable groups. This is reflected in the creation of the Just Transition Mechanism from the European Commission, a mechanism of more than 100 billion euros built to support the ecological transition in the most affected economic sectors and European regions. In this respect, Democratic Innovations (DI) must facilitate

the inclusion of citizens' voices and concerns regarding the fair distribution of the burdens and benefits of the ecological transition, address social tensions and ensure sustainable support from its citizens in the fight against climate change. The necessity of strong democratic consent (Lehne & Lehne, 2019) is consubstantial with the successful implementation of the EGD. However, this cannot be only a top-down dynamic. The problem is not for the rulers to better communicate the necessity of the ecological transition to the citizenry, nor for the DI to add some footnotes to the programs which have been adopted previously. The political and economic system to which consent must be developed cannot be taken for granted. DI must bring changes in the everyday life of lay citizens in order to be credible and interesting.

The PHOENIX project uses the six challenges as entry points to describe the different dimensions that future European deliberations on ecological and environmental issues can involve. In connection with **challenge (1) Time frame**, we propose ways of combining the time of democratic deliberation with the imperatives of ecological transition. The need for corrective indicators, the priority given to citizens' assemblies, but also the incorporation of these innovations into our national and European law are outlined here. Regarding **challenge (2) Complexity**, we encourage the formalisation and delimitation of expertise in relation to DI (Democratic Innovations). A minimum basis of scientific and rational consensus must be recognised before any deliberation, such as the existence of climate change and its anthropic origin, and in a second phase, disagreement between experts must also be formalised and presented to the participants, where the greater cognitive diversity should enable a better understanding in terms of responses and perspectives. For the **Scale challenge (3)**, we recommend multiplying DI experiments on a continental scale, while coupling them by integrating local and regional perspectives. The specific features of Europe's linguistic and cultural diversity need to be recognized and appreciated.

With regard to **challenge (4) on public participation**, we underline that the involvement of indigenous and overseas populations, as well as marginalised and disadvantaged groups, is particularly important when it comes to environmental topics. The issue of representation of future generations and non-humans is also discussed: we recommend giving priority to legal instruments to defend the interests of future generations and using DI to consider evolutions to the legal framework for non-humans and sentient beings. Finally, as a matter of inclusivity, we also recommend developing the links between the New Bauhaus European Initiative and the moments of collective exchange induced by DI. **Challenge (5) on conflict** leads us to work on the need to design deliberative processes that can be appropriated by social movements, mechanisms for recognizing minority opinions in DI, and the implementation of digital tools that can be easily adopted by people.

Finally, for **challenge (6) on the concept of Trust**, we worked on ways to avoid the emergence of so-called participatory authoritarianism in Europe³, by promoting DI on a large scale, including independent bodies to measure their effects, and by opening them up to citizen initiative. We also need to mobilise political parties and institutions, encouraging their use in their own internal operations. Finally, we need to ensure proper communication to create virtuous circles by showing citizens the positive effects of their participation in DIs on the struggle against climate change.

The PHOENIX project aims at exploring the potential of systemic deliberative and participatory turn into the European Green Deal. The definition and implementation of ecological transition policies on transnational and continental scale is a historic challenge. It requires a strong democratic legitimacy to be realised. Conversely, it may represent an exceptional opportunity to develop European democracy. The EU must create a new democratic model, potentially reproducible and inspiring, which includes institutional democratic innovation and encourages the emergence of a vibrant European civil society and the creation of a genuine European public sphere.

It is essential to emphasise that addressing the various democratic challenges and designing appropriate responses requires a systemic perspective. No single democratic participatory mechanism can be considered sufficient on its own. However, it is important to acknowledge that the concept of a system may change when implementing a deliberative and participatory approach and when considering the broader societal context. The different Tangrams that we will experiment with in our pilots will put together different methodologies as coherent a way as possible. Conversely, one must be realistic and understand that the EGD and these DI will face significant oppositions. A global systemic, transnational and transcalar perspective must conceive the society in which the EGD and DI should take place as ecosystems, full of cooperative moments but also of much more agonistic dynamics, with a lot of asymmetries of power and socially unjust relationships. If this is not sufficiently considered, one of the risks is to develop an unwanted managerial and top-down approach. Still, there are no shortcuts. The proof of our concept will be in the experiments we will conduct with our pilots.

³ Citizens' initiatives, without independent bodies capable of monitoring the long-term effects of these mechanisms, and as a solely administrative and presidential prerogative.

Table 1.1 - Main takeaways in relation to the six challenges

First set of challenges	Main takeaways
1. Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Where DI are related only to short-term topics, environmental and corrective indicators can be added. ● Citizens' assemblies are still the most effective way of achieving long-term decision-making. ● The incorporation of these DI needs to take place at an institutional level, in particular through constitutional amendments in member countries, and potentially at European level.
2. Complexity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The existence of conflicting opinions among experts should not be ignored, but recognised and formalised. ● Inclusivity and openness to the public can be used to enrich the perspectives and to enhance the cognitive diversity of the decision-making process. But this also presupposes broader action in the educational and media fields. ● Deliberations to implement climate policies presuppose the recognition of a minimum base of scientific and rational consensus on the existence of climate change.
3. Scale	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● We need to multiply DI experiments on a continental scale. Citizens' assemblies at European level must take into account both the national and EU scales. ● Specificities linked to national, linguistic and cultural differences must be recognized, formalised and integrated into these mechanisms. ● The use of these DIs must be transcalar, integrating local and regional perspectives, as well as those of rural and minority populations.

Second set of challenges	Main takeaways
4. Public participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The voice of indigenous populations, vulnerable populations and of the outermost and overseas populations must be integrated into these mechanisms, as well as immigrants and Roma populations. • The interests of future generations must be defended directly through legal tools, while DIs can be mobilised to think about the legal place of non-humans. • We need to have recourse to art and festivities, as well as to the New Bauhaus European Initiative, to make these moments of collective exchange more attractive and accessible, while enabling us to think about our relationship with the environment.
5. Conflict	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design mechanisms that can be used by social movements, not only to communicate with institutions, but also to enable the emergence of more horizontal and egalitarian social groups. • Recognise and formalise the existence of minority opinions. Provide the necessary support to enable minority groups to participate. • Implement digital tools that can be easily appropriated and cultivate a European democratic culture that recognizes and formalises conflict.
6. Trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To avoid the emergence of participatory authoritarianism, the EU must encourage the emergence of such mechanisms on a national and continental scale, with independent bodies to measure their long-term effects, and open these mechanisms up to citizens' initiatives. • Involve political parties and institutions in mobilising DI for their internal activities and as part of their political agenda. • Publicise and communicate on the impact of DI on the deployment of the Green Deal.

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1.2 Co-Design in principle, Territorial Commissions for Co-Design in practice

1.2.1 Co-Design in principle

The PHOENIX project places strong emphasis on the principle and practice of co-design as a means to enrich Democratic Innovations (EDIs). Understanding that one size does not fit all, the project recognises the need for co-designed participatory processes that can effectively engage and empower citizens and stakeholders. To achieve this, the Territorial Commissions for Co-Design have been conceived and established, providing citizens and stakeholders with a central role in shaping participatory processes that align with the unique characteristics of each territory, community, and environment. To augment their capacity and support their activities, PHOENIX developed and proposed its tangram approach displaying methods, tools and techniques as starting point for the co-design, promoting the cross-fertilisation among the TCCDs now and the co-designed pilots later. This section explores the significance of co-design in promoting democratic participation and empowerment, and its impact on the effectiveness and inclusivity of participatory processes.

Defining Co-Design in Democratic Innovations

Co-design is a collaborative approach that involves the active involvement of citizens and stakeholders in the design and development of processes, services, policies, or systems that directly involve and/or affect them. In the context of Democratic Innovations, co-design seeks to democratise the decision-making process by granting citizens and stakeholders an equal voice and role in shaping participatory mechanisms. By empowering individuals to actively participate in the design process, co-design goes beyond mere consultation and fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility among the participants.

Co-design, as a participatory approach, involves collaborative efforts between citizens, experts, and policymakers to develop democratic institutions that align with citizens' needs and aspirations. The co-design aims to create democratic innovations that are inclusive, deliberative, and responsive to the diverse needs and preferences of citizens. It emphasises transparency, accountability, and legitimacy by allowing multiple perspectives and diverse inputs to be considered in decision-making processes.

The multifaceted concepts of deliberative and participatory democracy serve as a fundamental theoretical foundation for co-design in democratic innovations. In particular, deliberative democracy posits that effective decision-making should involve reasoned and

inclusive dialogue among citizens and stakeholders. Co-design encourages open deliberation and fosters a more informed and well-considered public opinion, resulting in processes and policies that genuinely reflect the needs and values of citizens. Co-design aligns also with the principles of participatory governance, advocating for the direct involvement of citizens in policy formulation and implementation. Through co-design, citizens become active co-creators of democratic innovations, transcending mere consultation to actively influencing outcomes and shaping the rules of governance.

Effectiveness of Co-Design in Empowering Citizens

The research promoted by the PHOENIX project supports the co-design of democratic innovations to positively impact citizen empowerment and civic engagement. By involving citizens in the design process, we expected more inclusive processes, better outcomes and greater willingness to participate if compared to the traditional vertical design. This heightened engagement can strengthen the democratic fabric of the society and enhance citizens' trust in political institutions. PHOENIX co-design promotes inclusivity by inviting a diverse range of citizens to participate in decision-making and considerate diverse perspectives. While in participatory processes designed without co-design, marginalised voices are often overlooked or underrepresented, in contrast, the co-design approach acknowledges the importance of diverse perspectives and actively seeks to involve individuals from different socio-economic, cultural, and demographic backgrounds. This results in a more comprehensive and representative participatory process, leading to more powerful and equitable participation processes. The TCCD has been conceived to integrate into the design of democratic innovations the concerns of the communities, fostering a more equitable and just political system, beyond the traditional processes boundaries, promoting innovative mechanisms to represent the future generation and nature.

Furthermore, co-designed democratic innovations are more likely to produce effective and relevant policies. By drawing on the knowledge and experiences of citizens and stakeholders and involving them from the very beginning, co-design processes promote context-sensitive participatory processes that enhance the accuracy and practicality of proposed solutions, making them more likely to resonate with the needs of the population and effective in addressing local issues.

Challenges and Limitations of Co-Design

A significant challenge in co-design lies in power imbalances among stakeholders, citizens and (eventually) representatives from the institution(s). Policymakers and experts may dominate the process, marginalising the voices of citizens and community groups. PHOENIX addresses these imbalances requiring their TCCD to foster an environment that encourages equal participation and respectful dialogue.

Moreover, co-design processes can be time-consuming and resource-intensive, which might limit their implementation and impact. The PHOENIX project aims to support the co-design via its TCCD by providing methodological and technical support (via the tangram approach, the tools developed by the project and the technological support), resources (via the local partners) and planification to ensure the success of co-design initiatives.

Conclusion

Co-design empowers citizens by placing them at the centre of decision-making processes. In traditional models of democratic participation, citizens often feel disconnected and disengaged, leading to low levels of participation. However, when individuals are actively involved in the co-design of participatory processes, they become stakeholders in their truest sense, leading to higher levels of ownership and commitment. This empowerment extends beyond the process itself and can have a lasting impact on citizens' engagement in civic activities.

1.2.2 Territorial Commissions for Co-Design in practice

TCCDs are not closed bodies but rather deliberative processes of co-design of the participatory processes. Following the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach, each TCCD will contribute to the design of participatory and deliberative methodologies in collaboration with project partners. TCCD participants will also contribute to the selection of the Tangram components, which will determine the specific characteristics of the Enriched Democratic Innovations experienced.

According to the PHOENIX project Grant Agreement, the TCCD:

- Include **methodologies and tools** in order to visualise **future scenarios**.
- Foster **inclusiveness**, through the integration of perspectives of different actors and visions.
- Are **reflexive spaces** (involving different views, interests, and needs, including on themselves and its functioning).
- Are **responsive** institutes that search for solutions adequate to their territory, with the ambition to provide **solutions responsive** to challenges of the **EGD transition pathway**, but also to the functioning of **communication** and the relations with **conflicts** that can (pre)exist in the area and on the main topic of each pilot. This responsiveness applies also to its own functioning. In fact, as a collective and diversified body, the TCCD can help to also solve problems of their own architecture and functioning.
- Preserve their **diversity**, in terms of gender, age, diversity of origin, interests and perspective on the main topic – that is an important starting point to select some members. The topic is also useful for choosing how to ensure the engagement of marginalised voices (marginalisation refers not only to traditional vulnerable actors, but also to **areas of vulnerability** in relation to the specific topic). It is important that TCCD also include actors that represent pre-existing conflicts on EGD issues and of the main topic of that specific pilot.
- **Co-design** and/or contribute to each pilot participatory process respecting the guidelines and following as much as possible the timeline. The co-design phase of the TCCD necessarily precede the respective pilot implementation, then the Commissions accompany and **evaluate** it, particularly in order to give recommendations for **future replications**.

To pursue these tasks, PHOENIX project requests the TCCD to⁴:

- 1) Validate and co-design the participatory methodologies (evaluating and modifying the **tangram proposals**) and create the **rules** for its own functioning (e.g. timelines, cyclicity of meetings, substitutions and monitoring indicators, etc.).
- 2) Help build the most effective **communication** and **mobilisation** (e.g. giving opinion on tools, languages use, games etc.).
- 3) **Manage** potential problems, conflicts, and unexpected situations using their plural perspectives.
- 4) Choose and verify **informational dataset** to be released in each territory, and **test some tools** (e.g. ICTs platforms, games, questionnaires, surveys, etc.). before the approval of the pilots' final versions.
- 5) Co-design the **indicators to monitor each pilot** and its transformative capacity to define more solid Enriched Democratic Innovations.
- 6) Co-design the **evaluation of the pilot** as well as evaluate the **TCCD functioning and impact**.
- 7) Encourage the **dialogue with the other TCCDs** through inter-pilot dialogues, promoting **cross-fertilisation** between the tangrams and contributing to the final **policy recommendations** of the PHOENIX project.

⁴ Not all these functions must be done collectively by all the TCCDs; some can just involve some members, or "spokespersons" chosen by the TCCD. Additionally, each TCCD can add new functions - negotiated with its local partners - to reinforce their essence of co-design spaces with citizens and stakeholders.

TCCD models

Composition

Each TCCD should have approximately 15 members⁵ ensuring gender balance and it should have at least 30% of representatives of vulnerable groups⁶, distributed as follows:

- **1/3 representatives of territorial authorities** including the main administrative institution (reference scenario);
- **1/3 citizens** with different profiles;
- **1/3 stakeholders** including public organisations, trade unions, ONG, economic groups, social movements and practitioners.

If certain types of members are missing or if the implementer wishes to enhance the diversity of the TCCDs, collaboration with the pilot's main administration is crucial. Local partners can work together with the administration to identify potential additional members. Subsequently, they can either directly contact these individuals or, with the administration's approval, reach out to them independently. This cooperative effort ensures that the TCCD becomes more inclusive and representative, fostering a broader range of perspectives and insights during the co-design process.

⁵ A correct territorial representation is more important than a specific number of members. 10 or 20 members is fine as well.

⁶ Vulnerability includes those actors and areas which show specific environmental vulnerabilities, in relation to the main topics of the pilot (i.e. not just social vulnerabilities).

Citizens' engagement

When facing challenges in recruiting citizens or ensuring their continuous presence throughout the TCCD process, the following strategies can be employed:

- **Possible change of citizens during the process:** In this approach, there is a risk of having an unbalanced group in terms of demographics (age, gender, etc) as new citizens with different characteristics may join at different stages.
- **Other ways to engage citizens:** Utilising focus groups, public meetings, or involving elected representatives from citizens' assemblies can be effective in reaching a broader range of participants.
- **One-shot engagement** (single meeting): In cases where sustained participation is difficult, a one-time engagement, such as a single meeting, can still provide valuable insights and contributions from citizens.

By adopting these strategies, the TCCD can adapt to varying levels of citizen involvement and ensure that their voices are heard in the co-design process. It is important to select the most appropriate approach based on the specific challenges and context of each pilot territory to achieve meaningful and inclusive participatory processes.

Governance scenarios of the TCCD

To design the Territorial Commissions of Co-Design (TCCD), it is crucial to identify the typology of governance that will be applicable to the specific local conditions of each pilot territory. This typology encompasses three distinct scenarios:

1. **Reference scenario: "Inclusion"**. In this scenario, the governance of the pilot's process is guaranteed by a TCCD that includes both citizens and stakeholders. The local partner provides the framework for the TCCD, ensuring their involvement in the decision-making process.

2. **Scenario 2: “Collaboration”**. In this scenario, the governance of the process is organised and guaranteed by the main institution, seeking input and advice from the TCCD (comprising citizens and stakeholders) during the design phase. The local partner plays a significant role in setting up the TCCD's framework.

3. **Scenario 3: “Awareness”**. In this scenario, the governance of the process is assured and organised by the pilot partner of PHOENIX. Throughout the process, the local partner endeavours to generate increasing interest in involving stakeholders and citizens. The local partner provides assistance and observes the process, suggesting but not imposing the presence of citizens and stakeholders in the co-design. In the best situation, this scenario can evolve into scenario 2 during the implementation of the process.

Identifying the most appropriate governance typology for each pilot territory is essential for ensuring effective co-design and successful implementation of the Territorial Commissions of Co-Design. It enables a tailored approach that suits the unique local context and fosters meaningful participation of all relevant stakeholders and citizens in shaping democratic innovations.

2. PHOENIX PILOTS TANGRAMS

The Tangram approach developed by the PHOENIX project aims to construct a participatory process by combining various methodologies and tools, similar to assembling modules in a modular construction. This approach enables each participatory process to address different challenges related to participation and deliberation practices, such as inclusion, analysis, debate, and citizen control. All modules are seamlessly integrated into a coherent process, working towards a clear objective.

What sets this approach apart from other participatory processes is the inclusion of diverse methodologies and tools in each system. PHOENIX aims to make alternative modes of participation compatible and harness the positive aspects of different tools and methods. Each Tangram's objective is to achieve specific outcomes by skilfully blending multiple participatory modules.

By adopting the Tangram approach, the PHOENIX project seeks to foster innovative and effective participatory processes that adapt to the unique challenges and needs of each context, ultimately promoting more inclusive and impactful co-design experiences.

This section contains the following pilot summaries and tangram proposals:

- Portugal- Odemira
- Portugal-Tavira
- Portugal/ Spain-Gata-Malcata
- France-Rouen
- France-Debat Public
- Iceland
- Italy - Emilia Romagna
- Italy – Bologna
- Hungary - Central Transdanubia
- Hungary - Szeged
- Estonia-Tartu

Figure 2 – PHOENIX project map

Each pilot tangram is described in a two-pages policy brief. Note that the extended version of the information and elaboration contained in this section can be found in the Deliverable 3.2 *Methodologies for Democratic Innovations in Pilot context*.

2.1 Portugal - Odemira

When considering ecological transition scenarios, the municipality of Odemira presents a complex situation. It is an economically fragile municipality which is currently experiencing demographic changes linked to depopulation and progressive aging, with a high rate of elderly population in the municipality. Aside from social problems related to population dynamics, Odemira's economy is also threatened by the general economic investments and a great dependence on intensive agriculture. Climate change is also increasing the occurrence of extreme weather events such as floods, hurricane-force winds, and longer and more frequent droughts. These phenomena are perceived by citizens as clear indicators of climate change. The area is also prone to fires and there are additional dangers associated with water scarcity and conflicts between its various uses.

This proposal aims to build a general diagnosis of the municipality facing climate change challenges. Its objective is to identify existing problems and opportunities, while thinking about an action plan aimed at changing the municipality.

Stage 1. Self-diagnosis seeks to identify which problems intervention is more urgent, but also to connect actors. For this reason, this part of the process is oriented towards deepening inclusion and reinforcing participation. Moreover, it also aims to improve the perception of the complexity of ecological problems. For this, a specific participatory process of "socio-ecological memory" is proposed.

There are several tools used in this first phase. These include:

- Collective maps, as they are useful for diagnosing existing problems in a territory and promoting discussions and collective representations.
- Social maps, as they help visualise the state of social relations within the territory.
- Participatory workshops for each zone, to help develop a self-diagnosis of the situation in Odemira.
- Transects by bus, where the local population would take school buses during which they would exchange knowledge and work together to diagnose the problems in the area.
- Community tools for specific socio-demographic problems, to promote the inclusion of certain population groups that are usually excluded from participation processes, such as elderly population.
- Socio-ecological memory process around water, in order to develop a process to build a collective memory about water and the environment and review the narratives about the relationship between society and nature.

Stage 2. Evaluation and proposals is dedicated to evaluating the problems of Odemira municipality and on the elaboration of concrete proposals. The fact of collectively thinking about the future horizon using general criteria deliberately seeks to help the participants find common ground. Through different tools, participants will be encouraged to collectively think about common problems and possible alternatives. Working together, they will develop positive and negative scenarios on where they would like to see Odemira in x-number of years.

Once the future scenarios, positive and negative, are agreed upon, these can be converted into criteria that allow the desired scenario to be translated into an action plan. This can help a lot later when it comes to prioritising specific proposals. The next step would be to commence the collection of proposals which must be aimed at improving the negative scenario to try to get a positive one. This can be done through a set of workshops.

Stage 3. Decision making process has to do with the decision-making process and/or the prioritisation of the proposals following the criteria established in the second phase. The use of online and offline tools will promote greater inclusion in the decision-making process. The participatory budget already existing in the municipality can be used as a decision-making tool and can be used alongside a digital platform. This will ensure that they are able to be consulted by the population of Odemira. Likewise, a document will be sent to all addresses with the proposals and a place will be sought for dissemination in the media.

Stage 4. Municipal Action Plan involves the elaboration of a municipal Action Plan that would integrate all the stakeholders of the municipality, as well as a significant representation of the participants. An Action Plan seeks to carry out a debate on the detailed actions that must be undertaken in order to execute a specific proposal. It can be carried out through participatory forums in which the responsibility that the different actors in the municipality is identified, as well as the different actions that each one would have to do so that a specific proposal could finally be executed.

2.2 Portugal - Tavira

Tavira, as other parts of the Algarve region, presents a scenario of high vulnerability with respect to the impacts of climate change. This scenario is especially relevant if we consider the problem of water, such as the decrease in water availability and its quality, floods and rise in sea level. Equally, there are both economic and sociodemographic issues that affect the region, such as heavy dependency on agriculture and tourism, as well as the ageing population. This is a particular issue in regard to climate change, as the local population often shows reluctance to alter their ways of life and does not seem to have much confidence in the action of the municipality in this area.

The challenges that the municipality faces can be addressed through the system of food gardens and orchards from which to promote transition practices and policies linked to the EGD. Food gardens can promote different practices of participation and innovation that take advantage of the strategic intersections between organic agriculture and sustainable food. The promotion of organic agriculture on a community scale can allow the generation of new ideas about more sustainable lifestyles and, above all, it can make it more accessible to citizens. Food gardens are also highly sensitive spaces with respect to water management, its availability, quality and scarcity. In this way, community practices will have to directly confront the management of this resource, being able to socialise and disseminate new water cultures.

Stage 1. Regulation and mapping

This first phase has three objectives. The first is to map the spaces in the municipality that may be suitable for hosting food gardens. The second is to analyse the society-nature relationship that exists and has existed in relation to those spaces. The third is to establish, in a participatory manner, a shared regulatory framework for all food gardens.

The process begins with the completion of a set of walks (transects) that will make it possible to identify which are the spaces where food gardens could be housed. During these walks, these spaces can be located, identified, photographed and analysed. These can then be uploaded onto an online platform. On said platform, a space can be opened to upload comments or information regarding said locations. This systematisation of spaces must be carried out with the support of the local government and with entities interested in the subject, in order to include the most relevant spaces onto the list. Moreover, it will also aim to include the population usually excluded from these processes (older population,

migrants, women and children and youth fundamentally) and examine how they perceive the society-nature relationship.

There are two tools used in this first phase. These include:

- Transect, that is, walks with the local population to diagnose the problems of a certain area through the exchange of knowledge that takes place during the walk.
- Collective maps, to promote debate on the forms of use and on the ways of understanding the territory in which a specific project is developed and help inform decision-making.

Stage 2. Coordination and design

The second phase of the process seeks to establish the process of systematising different types of knowledge regarding food gardens and the design of a system of shared resources. It will rely on tools such as:

- Citizens Labs, which will enable collaboration between people who hold diverse knowledge (professional, experiential...) from different fields (from academic to more amateur practices), with the idea of creating collaborative practices among them to respond to problems in real life.
- Social maps, which will help identifying the different actors in the municipality (both governmental and individual) and the relationships they have between them in relation to the management of food gardens.
- Participatory workshops, to analyse the determining factors in one of the existing urban gardens. This can be followed by the advancement of the design of urban gardens through the following strategies:
 - Holding an open competition in which different interdisciplinary teams can present proposals for the design of one or more food gardens.
 - Expanding the practice of citizen laboratories to different food gardens.
 - Developing a toolbox so that those who participate in the food gardens can design them directly.

Stage 3. Food gardens in the ecological transition of Tavira

This third phase is proposed once the food gardens are up and running and have begun to develop their activity. It is a moment of reflection on the process that aims to improve the gardens within a set of consensuses on how they influence the ecological transition of the city.

To achieve this, it is proposed to run scenario workshops with the objective of thinking about common problems and possible alternatives. The activity begins by first grouping the participants into small groups. In the different groups formed, everyone thinks about the

positive and negative characteristics that a future scenario would have. When the debate in the small groups ends, they proceed to a sharing of each of the scenarios whose characteristics are then synthesised.

2.3 Portugal/ Spain - Gata-Malcata

The Serra da Malcata and the Sierra de Gata are a cross-border area that share a landscape, potentials, and problems. Both are rural areas, sparsely populated, and with very fragile economies. The area has been chosen as a pilot as it represents an “ecoregion”, i.e. a relatively large unit of land and/or water that is characterised by a distinctive climate, ecological features and plant and animal communities. In both areas, there is a shared vision of environmental risks, which the population experiences on a daily basis. Both territories share many of the environmental risks caused by climate change. Both territories are highly aware of their situation and the vulnerability of the territory they inhabit.

From this perspective, this project proposes the creation of a cross-border space (build a Cross-border Wildfire Observatory (WFO) aimed at mitigating fires and providing land use transformations that can also contribute to wildfire prevention, water conservation, new forms of energy production and international co-operation. Thinking about the construction of a shared institution will facilitate cooperation between both regions, as well as promote participative action between both territories. The objective of this joint construction would be to take advantage of all the practices that are already carried out on both sides of the border, share all the knowledge that is available (from civil society organisations, researchers and people) and open a space that allows the presentation of proposals and initiatives aimed at combating or mitigating fires and water scarcity.

Stage 1. Autodiagnosis

The objective of this phase is to know and systematise the knowledge, practices and experiences that exist today in both territories from the point of view of fires, forest management and water scarcity. This includes gathering all the experiences and initiatives that exist today in both territories aimed at mitigating fires as well as examining the perception that citizens have of the problem of fires, as well as the solutions or alternatives that they propose to tackle it.

There are several tools used in this first phase. These include:

- Participatory workshops, to get a sense of what the public highlights as negative and positive in the area.
- Collective maps, to promote debate on the forms of use and on the ways of understanding the territory in which a specific project is developed and help inform decision-making.
- Social maps, to better understand existing conflicts and provide us with valuable information to better understand the strategies to be followed in order to implement specific actions in the future.

- Digital debate, to broaden access and involve as many members of the public as possible.
- Systematisation, which is about ordering the information, identifying the common elements, differences, and the features with which the territory would be characterised.

Stage 2. Future scenarios, proposals and general criteria

The second phase begins to work with all the information systematised in the self-diagnosis phase. The objective here is to obtain proposals for action aimed at laying the foundations of the WFO, while the framework made up of general criteria that will translate into a development plan is built up.

This can be achieved through:

- Scenario workshops, where a diverse as possible group of participants is divided into groups to think about the positive and negative characteristics that a future scenario would have. These insights can then be converted into criteria that allow the desired scenario to be translated into operational actions.
- Collection of proposals concerned with combating the fires, through the use of digital platforms or participatory workshops.

Stage 3. Decision making process and Action Plan for the Wildfire Observatory

The third phase of this proposal would have the objective of prioritising the proposals through the creation of a participatory budgeting in the cross-border area. In this way, all the inhabitants could easily participate in the prioritisation of the proposals that emerged throughout the previous process.

The main objective of this stage is to design an action program that adequately defines the tasks that would have to be done to implement a specific proposal, while establishing the actors that would be involved in its development. What is sought with the Action Plan is to discuss how the proposals made can be implemented.

From here, the WFO can supervise the implementation of the proposals. However, this phase also makes it possible to generate information that can be shared among the population in order to make it easier for citizens to supervise the actions.

2.4 France - Rouen

The Rouen metropolis and the Haute-Normandie area in general have shown a continuous increase in temperature in recent years, together with a relevant decrease in available water (especially due to rainfall). Future scenarios for this area are especially critical with respect to these two elements:

- A significant increase in heat waves and days of high temperatures.
- An increase in dry days, but also in extreme phenomena such as heavy rainfall and floods.

Moreover, the municipality faces additional challenges related to nuclear energy dependency, the lack of food sovereignty, high poverty rate and high private vehicle usage, which further contributes to making it the most polluted city in France.

The challenges that the metropolis faces have a lot to do with how metropolitan planning can take advantage of the potential of the territory when it comes to the use of renewable energy and the development of organic. The territory of the metropolis offers possibilities to face the high dependence on nuclear energy and its scarce food sovereignty, but it requires an articulated and comprehensive planning to be able to take advantage of them.

In Rouen, as has happened with the whole of France, there have been conflicts linked to the deepening of inequalities linked to the ecological transition or conflicts over the necessary transformations in lifestyles. The development of participatory processes requires improving their inclusiveness to prevent the ecological transition from generating greater social inequality and educate people on the correlation between EGD and the general improvement of quality of life.

To tackle this, this project proposes the integration of several municipalities aimed at building a community of assemblies that will improve the adaptation of these assemblies to the challenges of the EGD.

Stage 1. Proposals and delegates

This stage starts with each one of the municipal Assemblies choosing proposals that refer to the field of competences that correspond to the municipality to the metropolitan region. This does not limit the type of proposals that can be made in each Assembly, they simply seek to clarify these two spheres of competence to improve possible coordination. The election of delegates must be carried out considering the set of seven assemblies, guaranteeing the diversity of each case. This can be done either by draw or by voting.

Stage 2. Coordination

This stage is composed of several different approaches. This includes:

- Citizens labs, composed of representatives of the municipal assemblies, which will work on the development and justification of the different proposals, with the objective of presenting them in the Metropolitan Citizen Assembly, as well as improving the possibilities of implementation of the proposals.
- Local assemblies, where the delegates of the municipal assemblies can hold open forums in their respective territories in which to present the set of proposals and the axes of the debates of the Metropolitan Assembly. This helps broaden public participation.
- Self-managed assemblies, which will allow for not only the broadening of the participating public, but also to broaden the inputs through which the Metropolitan Assembly can prepare its proposals. In particular, this will increase the engagement of specific population groups (young people, women, migrants) or representatives of interest, such as very specific professional groups or social movements that can contribute knowledge not considered for the analysis of proposals or for the preparation of new proposals.
- Metropolitan Assembly, which will consist of 75 participants receiving different reports prepared by the group of representatives of the municipal assemblies, together with the set of proposals prepared by the self-convened assemblies or local forums.

Stage 3. Evaluation and monitoring

This last phase is intended to establish the coordination and evaluation system for the proposals of the Assembly and its possible continuity. Three organisations are proposed:

- Follow-up of the proposals: a group of 15 people will have semi-annual meetings with the public administrations in order to know the status of the proposals. The response of the administrations will be mandatory and will be public.
- A knowledge systematisation group: this group will interview participants from the different assemblies and their organising teams, with the aim of systematising relevant learning for the development and coordination of participatory/deliberative processes.
- Possibility of calling new debates: 30% of the participants in the Citizen Assembly and the TCCD may propose new debates related to this process and participate in their co-design.

2.5 France - Debat Public

France is one of the largest economies in the world, with extraordinary social and economic development. Moreover, climate change poses a major challenge, with temperatures across France steadily rising. There are also socio-demographic challenges, related to its ageing population. The challenges that France faces are multiple, but to address the issue of supporting EGD, it is proposed that the focus should be on energy combining elements that are crucial for France. France is currently reliant on nuclear generators to produce energy so increasing efforts are required to expand renewables.

The French government is finalising the possibility of installing maritime windmills along the French coast. The possibility of organising a public debate on its installation would help to put the question of renewable energy sources in the public debate, while at the same time it would be possible to reflect on its limits. The engagement of citizens could be the base for a wide public debate about energy in France. The installation of maritime windmills would make it possible to address energy mix in a broad way to think about how to face the challenges coming along with the climate change and ageing process in French society.

From the point of view of the challenges facing France, this project proposes a broad debate about the impacts of the installation of maritime windmills. The participatory process uses different tools to reach a wide public diversity, including vulnerable population, to know public opinion about the best maritime areas to build wind farms.

Stage 1. Debate on general criteria for a future installation of maritime wind farm

This stage would take place over a weekend or two, since the objective is not to make recommendations, but to decide on general criteria that guide future consultation in the second stage of the Tangram. There would be 4 consecutive debate states.

- 1) Once the participants are selected by lottery, this first sequence of the debate would have the objective of inviting all the participants to discuss the risks and difficulties of installing offshore wind farms. The objective is not for the participants to be able to elaborate a risk map in detail as soon as they start, but rather to start a debate based on the preconceived ideas that they already have.
- 2) In the second stage of the debate, the already selected experts would show their different positions on the installation of offshore wind farms.
- 3) The third stage would consist of the participants debating in a broad way the different perspectives previously heard. This phase of the debate can be prolonged as deemed appropriate, always mixing the debate between small groups and in plenary. It can also be organised with the experts to encourage exchange between them and the participants.

Stage 2. Co-design of a role-playing game for the inclusion of non-human perspectives

Stage 2 involves the creation of a role-playing game as it allows for non-human proposals to be regarded within the debate. Role-playing games are one of the most consolidated strategies to represent the non-human universe within participatory processes, as it enables the participants to reflect on how deliberation processes can serve to represent some non-human spheres in the deliberation, power dynamics within the human/non-human relationship, possible forms of human/non-human cooperation, and the non-human agency. To ensure accuracy, it should entail:

- Child representation, given the special sensitivity of childhood to recognise the agency of the non-humans.
- Ecological social movements and, especially, animal rights.
- University specialists who work in non-human agency.
- University or social movement specialists who work on sea phenomena that may be related to the agenda of the process.
- Game specialists.
- Citizens not linked to any of these areas, ideally coming from the four coast areas where the windmills would be installed.
- Desirably, there should be moments of work on some gameplay with non-humans directly, such as non-human animals, plants, and objects.

Stage 3. Public opinion about best areas and veto zonas for wind farms

This stage focuses on collecting specific proposals concerning the best areas to install marine mills, relying on tools such as participatory workshops, collective maps, and digital debate. They each allow either for the ability to either broaden participation or to help participants reach a final decision.

Stage 4. Synthesis.

The objective of this phase is to synthesise all the information supplied in stage 1, 2 and 3. It is very possible that contradictory information is collected, because when organising different meetings always with the same objective, opposing views may arise. It is at this moment that the general criteria obtained in the first phase offer us a tool to resolve the contradictions.

2.6 Iceland - National pilot

One of the most relevant impacts of climate change in Iceland is the increase in temperatures. Another of the impacts has to do with fishing, which is one of the foundations of the Icelandic economy, and which can be particularly affected by changes in the oceans. Iceland presents several relevant ecological conflicts, many of them structured around the conflict regarding land uses. Conflicts over land use have to be framed in a context of land degradation through soil erosion and low presence of forests. In this conflict, those that focus on new energy infrastructures are confronted with those that bet on the conservation of nature. Moreover, the scenario of the conflict over land use is aggravated by the importance of tourism in the Icelandic economy, tourism highly structured around nature-based leisure activities.

This project proposes to tackle the conflicts around land use, as one of the best opportunities that exist to start ecological transition that can encourage citizens to engage with it. Although citizen awareness regarding climate change has increased, citizens remain somewhat reluctant when it comes to committing to the ecological transition. For some, it is because they do not want to give up to certain levels of well-being, and that there is little confidence in the impact of the changes at the individual level. For others, it has to do with the uncertainty presented by the transition pathway, which does not have a clear route and a coherent set of actions.

Stage 1. Diagnosis, Land Use Game and future scenarios

This first phase is focused on the use of the 'Landsleikurinn' – Land Use Game. In each of these workshops, teams will be created that will play the game and that will have to justify and publicly expose their decisions. In this way, the team will be able to systematise the opinions of the participants and identify potential conflicts.

This will be accompanied by transects (walks through a local area to identify problems), surveys with tourists (to get external perspective on local land use), collective maps (to develop understanding of how territory is perceived, used and how this can be improved), and scenarios workshops (to get participants to collectively think about common problems and solutions).

Stage 2. Co-design of a role-playing game for the inclusion of non-humans

Stage 2 involves the creation of a role-playing game as it allows for non-human proposals to be regarded within the debate. Role-playing games are one of the most consolidated strategies to represent the non-human universe within participatory processes, as it enables the participants to reflect on how deliberation processes can serve to represent some non-human spheres in the deliberation, power dynamics within the human/non-

human relationship, possible forms of human/non-human cooperation, and the non-human agency.

Stage 3. Citizen Assembly (CA)

The Citizen Assembly's objective is for ordinary people to jointly decide the most appropriate measures of action within a specific field of public policies. Sessions within a CA continuously combine small group discussion and plenary discussion with participants and experts in fields under discussion. Plenary debates are usually organised to listen to experts which is then followed by small-group discussion in order to continue advancing on the problem. This is followed by a debate on the citizen proposals. The key objective of these discussions would be to find positive and negative justifications of the different measures, as well as the consequences and implications of the application of each one. In the event that the measures were not previously proposed, the justification helps the participants to think about the adequacy of the proposals they prepare.

To broaden participation, the CA participants can also hold open forms in their local area in Tartu, which will help analyse conflicts linked to proposals and generate discussion around them. They can also set up self-managed assemblies to further assist with proposal preparation. Additionally, to improve the inclusion of non-human perspectives, an artistic space will be created. This installation is a garden in which you can feel the emotions of the plants that live in said garden. It will be opened to the general public, and it will make it easier for the members of the CA to experience and consider non-human agency when making their suggestions.

Once this is completed, it is necessary to build recommendations. This is achieved by giving each group measures discussed by another group in the previous step. The task of the group should be to criticise the proposed measures with their appropriate justifications. All criticisms are publicly displayed, helping all the participants to visualise their work from the perspective of other participants. The final dynamic would consist of each small group rethinking their original measurements in light of the criticisms made by the other participants. The final recommendations would be voted on and prioritised at the end of the CA.

Stage 4. Evaluation and monitoring

This last phase is intended to establish the follow-up system for the proposals of the Assembly and its possible continuity. Two organizations are proposed:

- Follow-up of the proposals: a group of 10 people will have semi-annual meetings with the public administrations in order to know the status of the proposals. The response of the administrations will be mandatory and will be public.
- Possibility of calling new debates: 30% of the participants in the Citizen Assembly may propose new debates related to this process and participate in their co-design.

2.7 Italy - Emilia Romagna

Emilia Romagna is a region where some of the effects of climate change are beginning to be clearly perceived: increases in temperatures, decreases in rainfall and, especially in recent years, the proliferation of extreme water phenomena such as floods. Given this climate vulnerability, Emilia Romagna has become one of the most active regions when it comes to promoting initiatives to respond to the ecological crisis. Nevertheless, citizen awareness of climate change is very low. It is especially young people and the upper-middle classes who are more aware of it and are more predisposed to change their habits. The rest of the population perceives significant financial problems to get involved in the ecological transition. Other issues include high dependency on private transport, which helps generate pollution and poor air quality, as well as high dependency on imported energy and loss of biodiversity.

To tackle these challenges, this project will combine long-term planning mechanisms with mechanisms for prioritising proposals related to more short-term democratic innovations. It will help establish a dialogue between generations on memory and territory, and to include a diverse audience in the proposal preparation process.

Stage 1. Diagnosis and development of shared scenarios

The objective of this first part is to define the strategic scenarios shared by the different municipalities that will guide decision-making. For this, a crowdsourcing platform will be used, where users will be able to use different thematic sections to select the most relevant objectives. There will also be face-to-face process where local assemblies will be able to define the shared planning scenarios. These assemblies will deal with issues that all municipalities can share.

This stage will rely on the use of participatory workshops, to get a sense of the situation in the region and the expectations of the inhabitants. The objective of this process is to agree on common criteria that guide the proposals of the third phase of the process, as well as criteria that serve to weigh the different proposals and determine their choice.

Stage 2. Intergenerational process, memory and future

The objective of this stage is to activate a process of intergenerational dialogue. This process will help us to activate a discussion on the future of the territory between different audiences, especially that of young people and the older population.

The first phase is the selection of educational centres. An educational centre will be selected in each of the participating municipalities, trying to uphold the criteria of diversity. The first phase will aim to compose a memory of the territory, interviewing actors who lived there for a considerable period in time. This will be achieved through:

- Collective interviews carried out by the students of the centres.
- Compilation of graphic material.
- Home notebook, so that the students can work with the families, answer questions, and collect family testimonies.
- EMPAVILLE game can also be used to enhance the acquisition of participatory skills.

Once this first phase is completed, each of these centres will develop at least one transect in the area as a tool to organise onsite inspections. This will be open to participation to all other students as well as the family, relatives and friends of the rest of the participants in the first phase. Moreover, the transect will be elaborated collectively by the students and the older population and will try to contrast these elements of citizen memory with the current state in the territory. It is recommended that public authorities or scientific experts attend the transect to answer any possible doubts about the state of the area.

This will be followed by the creation of a territory manifesto, where students will use this knowledge to elaborate a 10-point manifesto that includes what the territory should be like. Parallel to this, an inter-educational centre team will be created that will create an exhibition in which the material collected can be seen, both that related to the lifting of the citizen memory of the territory as well as the elaboration of the manifestos.

Stage 3. Participatory Budgeting

Once the first two phases have been completed, proposals will be prepared based on a participatory budgeting process that will have both virtual and face-to-face to maximise inclusion and the quality of the process. This will be done through Citizen Laboratories, Participatory Budgeting assemblies in each municipality, and online voting. When the proposals have been voted, the proposals that have exceeded 51% approval will be selected and weighed against the criteria developed in the first phase of the process. The proposals with the most votes will be budgeted to decide which can be undertaken under existing financial limitations.

Stage 4. Evaluation and monitoring

Two types of monitoring bodies will be formed:

- One made up of participants in the process in the schools, in charge of supervising the proposals derived from this process. This body will be in charge of drawing up a communication strategy on said follow-up.
- One made up of participants in the process of inter-municipal assemblies and participatory budgeting. This body will be in charge of drawing up a communication strategy on said follow-up.

2.8 Italy – Bologna

The city of Bologna faces several challenges related to climate change. There is an uneven distribution of awareness about climate change, with young people and upper middle class displaying the greatest awareness. High dependency on private transport helps generate pollution and its separation and efficient management of waste is below national standards. There is also little quality and availability of public spaces and green spaces in various parts of the city. It is also susceptible to flooding and has very little energy sovereignty based on the use of renewable sources.

The challenges that the municipality faces have a lot to do with the articulation of the different processes that currently exist linked to the energy transition and other areas related to climate change. This proposal will help frame some issues of the debate on the future of the Neighbourhood Houses (CDQ) within the framework of the ecological transition and the EGD. It will also improve the inclusion of the population that, for the moment, has been considered as strategic in the discussion processes on the future of the CDQ: the elderly, adolescents, second generations and people with disabilities.

Stage 1. Agenda development

In this phase, the themes that will organise both the diagnostic process and the preparation of the proposals will be defined. One of the objectives of this phase of the process has to do with relating future reflections of the CDQs to two especially representative projects in the city: the results of the Citizen Assembly for the Climate (with the prospect of concluding at the end of 2023) and the Carbon Neutral Missions project. This will be done through participatory workshops which will define areas of work that are common to the different CDQs participating in the process. This will provide the basis for the different forms of cooperation that follow.

Stage 2. Self-diagnosis

This phase of the process has a more individual/domestic/family starting point, which consists of preparing a notebook on the relationship between the daily life of the participants and the CDQ, both in the present and in the future.

This stage is composed of several different approaches. This includes:

- Transect – to identify issues that have to do with architecture, the construction of the space, the infrastructure on which it rests (for example, energy or waste management resources) or the practices that are carried out in CDQs.
- Collective maps – to identify what representations exist around the CDQ, how people imagine that they work, what practices take place and how proposals can be made to change said imaginaries.

- Citizen labs – to help promote collaboration between people who hold diverse knowledge, come from diverse backgrounds and work in diverse fields with the idea of creating collaborative practices among them to respond to problems in real life.
 - To make the approach to the future of the CDQ more inclusive, it will also include non-human perspectives through a serious game (a role-playing game) to develop non-human proposals within the process.

Stage 3. Diagnosis and deliberation scenario

This stage starts through a *Junk Playgrounds to imagine the Future* game. It will be supported by the schools close to the different participating CDQs. The idea is to generate one or several groups of young people of school age for each of the CDQs. The objective is for them to generate a model of the CDQs that can be walked around and that can be manipulated.

During this stage, a workshop will also be held in each of the CDQs for the preparation of a diagnosis shared by the entire CDQ. Once a shared diagnosis has been established, the workshop will close with the preparation of a Social Map, which will help visualise the state of social relations within the territory and what kinds of actions can be taken to improve these relationships.

Stage 4. Proposals

The last phase has to do with the preparation of proposals for each of the CDQs, as well as the establishment of forms of coordination between them. It will start from the review of the systematised diagnosis in stage 3, and it will be held in the environment of the Junk Playground previously designed. This will be achieved through a Participatory Workshop, which will include each one of the inter-CDQ working groups will be responsible for organising a part of the workshop linked to their field of work, game play to include non-human perspective, and drawing up a social map of all the actors not participating in the CDQs with whom relationships can be established based on the proposals.

This will be followed by a coordination stage between the different CDQ, aimed at analysing common problems among the different CDQs and at establishing organisational systems. Through a workshop, participants will be asked to group those common proposals between the different CDQs as well as establish the coordination system of the different CDQs to improve the management of these proposals.

Likewise, the event will have a festive character oriented fundamentally to the establishment of links between members of the CDQ and the development of a shared identity.

2.9 Hungary - Central Transdanubia

Transdanubia faces important challenges. It is heavily dependent on agriculture which poses many problems in the region associated with the intensive use of water resources and the pollution produced by the intensive use of fertilisers. Water scarcity and pollution is also a recurring problem, and it is becoming increasingly felt with an increase in extreme weather events. Extremely hot days have increased, there are fewer days of rain per year and periods of drought have increased, which has caused an increase in water stress. This is one of the main concerns of the population. Water scarcity can become a source of significant conflict in the region. Water problems are also affected by mass tourism, as there is a need for increased water resources.

The challenges that the region faces have a lot to do with the use of water. This project proposes to tackle this by creating an organic food production network. Organic agriculture does not depend on fertilisers that contaminate groundwater and does not erode the soil therefore favouring greater water absorption and increased humidity that allows reducing the amount of water needed. This activity would also facilitate the integration between different profiles of people, who do not necessarily share objectives, but are attracted by the appeal of healthier produce being available.

Stage 1. Selection of the general criteria among all the actors involved

The first stage builds the participatory agricultural production label (Participatory Guarantee System-PGS). The basis for PGS is a jointly established definition of the term “organic production” or, in other words, producers have to decide which criteria they wish to emphasise in its quality assurance system. A participatory workshop will be held with the objective of building and prioritising the criteria of the PGS.

Stage 2. Selection of the procedures by which the PGS will make decision

The second step is for PGS to define their decision-making procedures. The basic procedure is monthly general assemblies, during which specific tasks are assigned to specific committees. The creation of a PGS needs to create a governance system capable of making decisions about the management and strategies of the system. Within a participatory system such as the PGS, the final decision rests with a general assembly that approves or rejects the measures that are submitted to the assembly. Committee composition can be rotated to ensure everyone participates in each of the PGS’ committees at some point in time. The rotation of positions would guarantee the change of people within each committee, which facilitates greater transparency.

Committees can be designed following a workshop. All participants meet and are divided into small groups. Each group discusses a specific number of committees needed to manage the system. Each committee has to be conveniently justified according to the functions it would perform. Once all committees are defined, it would be necessary to define more succinctly their functions, how often they meet, as well as the way to rotate the participants among all the committees.

Stage 3. Selection of the procedures that will serve to guarantee the quality of agricultural production

The third step is to define the quality assurance procedure. Collective visits to member farms are a key element. Here it is necessary to establish the norms and criteria that will be used to evaluate the production methods that the farmer has followed on each farm. Approval of these methods implies obtaining the PGS quality seal. The evaluation methods have to be linked to the general criteria approved in the first phase.

In this case, the citizen laboratories tool can be used to develop two distinct committees: one that is responsible for visiting the target farm and a second one that evaluates the report of the visit, taking into account past visits reports. After the participants' discussions, this double step system pursues several objectives. First, it reduces the mistakes that could be committed by a single evaluator. Second, it guarantees a collective process of decision-making and responsibility assumption. Thirdly, it dilutes conflicts or personal favouritism effects on the guarantee process.

The objective of creating a PGS is to build a framework of trust between producers and consumers following sustainable agricultural practices. One of the biggest opportunities of a PGS is the creation and maintenance of short marketing channels (farm to fork). PGS allows the consumer community to be involved in quality monitoring and evaluation, being a voice in the evaluation and decision-making process of the PGS system. Consumers could be incorporated in any of the construction phases of the PGS. PGS also makes it possible to support a local food market that sells the food produced.

2.10 Hungary - Szeged

The city of Szeged faces several different challenges. The city is crossed by two rivers. Their geographical configuration has historically caused an accumulation of sewage, causing significant pollution. Inland waters became a major problem in a flat and humid region due to historically poor water management. Increased droughts and increased water scarcity due to climate change have worsened the problem, frequently causing significant problems in both urban and agricultural areas. According to forecasts, the city and its region within Hungary will continue to be the most affected by drought, desertification, low rainfall, and rising temperatures, especially in summer. In this context, water is a vulnerable resource in the region, even more so because the health of the Tisza River depends on its neighbouring countries. It is also heavily reliant on agriculture, which increases the demand for water at a time when the scarcity is already appreciable, especially in summer. Many industries are associated with the agri-food sector, which is why they not only generate wealth and jobs, but also food, which poses significant tensions.

Following the challenges Szeged faces, the objective of this project is to encourage a public debate on the risks, so that it is possible to publicly address the problems. Based on a shared diagnosis of the situation, this participatory process is aimed at thinking about solutions and alternatives to the problems that have been raised.

Stage 1. Public debate about Szeged challenges

This stage will focus on identifying the main problems of Szeged. It proposes to combine different tools that allow us to recognize and give prominence to knowledge that is usually excluded from the debate on public policies.

This will include:

- Collective maps, which will be used to promote debate on the forms of use and on the ways of understanding the territory.
- Scenarios workshop, where participants will be divided into groups and think about the positive and negative characteristics that a future scenario would have. This will be used to develop criteria that can be used to develop an action plan and prioritising specific proposals.
- Comic prize, which will help get young people involved in highlighting the challenges of the region.
- Digital debate, which will help broaden public participation.

Stage 2. TCCD and agenda setting

The objective of the second phase is to order all the information from stage 1, analyse it and discuss the problems identified by the population of Szeged. The ultimate goal would be to set the agenda for the Citizen Assembly. This stage would also encompass information synthesis activity to summarise the diversity of opinions and perceptions that people have about the environmental challenges that they face that were raised in stage 1.

Stage 3. Citizen Assembly

The Citizen Assembly's objective is for ordinary people to jointly decide the most appropriate measures of action within a specific field of public policies. Sessions within a CA continuously combine small group discussion and plenary discussion with participants and experts in fields under discussion. It is advisable to distribute the participants in small groups randomly. Plenary debates are usually organised to listen to experts which is then followed by small-group discussion in order to continue advancing on the problem. It is not necessary to reach an agreement at this initial moment; instead, it is about discussing the advantages and disadvantages of the different visions of the experts from the point of view of the participants.

This is followed by a debate on the citizen proposals. The key objective of these discussions would be to find positive and negative justifications of the different measures, as well as the consequences and implications of the application of each one. If the measures were not previously proposed, the justification helps the participants to think about the adequacy of the proposals they prepare.

Once this is completed, it is necessary to build recommendations. This is achieved by giving each group measures discussed by another group in the previous step. The task of the group should be to criticise the proposed measures with their appropriate justifications. All criticisms are publicly displayed, helping all the participants to visualise their work from the perspective of other participants. The final dynamic would consist of each small group rethinking their original measurements in light of the criticisms made by the other participants. The final recommendations would be voted on and prioritised at the end of the CA.

Stage 4. Evaluation and monitoring

This last phase is intended to establish the follow-up system for the proposals of the CA and its possible continuity. Two organisations are proposed:

- Follow-up of the proposals: a group of 10 people who will have semi-annual meetings with the public administrations in order to know the status of the proposals. The response of the administrations will be mandatory and will be public.
- Possibility of calling new debates: 30% of the participants in the Citizen Assembly may propose new debates related to this process and participate in their co-design.

2.11 Estonia-Tartu

Tartu is a medium-sized city, in a country where half of the territory is forest and there is an abundance of surface water. The attitudes towards ecological transition in Tartu are ambivalent. Tartu has a historical legacy of using non-renewable and highly polluting fossil fuels. The country has one of the highest rates of per capita greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. On the other hand, Tartu presents a scenario with high possibilities to start the ecological transition. The population is highly aware of the value of the natural environment. The organic agriculture sector is being developed and there is a promotion of it through public purchasing processes. The challenges facing the city of Tartu are not just environmental. The population shows signs of disconnection with public activities. There is participatory fatigue, which translates into significant resistance to getting involved in public activities. All of this highlights the difficulties that the city is facing, since the green transition requires significant popular support, capable of facing the risks that a transition to less polluting growth models entails.

To tackle these problems, this proposal seeks to create a Sustainable Food System. It is argued that SFS will help transition towards more sustainable models of development with a significant impact on increasing food sovereignty, as well as on eating and environmental practices.

Stage 1: Autodiagnosis

The transition to a sustainable food system has broad implications for all aspects of daily life in a city. A change of direction in public policies can therefore face much resistance from the population. That is why carrying out a self-diagnosis is important to build a framework of action shared with citizens.

This can be done through surveys in schools, which will help collect information on people's habits concerning food consumption and all the relationships that are established in relation to it: budget that is dedicated to food with respect to the money available; type of food taken; resistances and barriers to eating healthier foods, etc. This approach will make the children researchers, making them essential participants in the process of information gathering, systematisation, and recommendations production. This can also be accompanied by the use of a role-playing game, so that children can experience the difficulties and virtues of a discussion process, digital debates and focus groups with food stakeholders and adult population.

Stage 2. Citizen Assembly

The Citizen Assembly's objective is for ordinary people to jointly decide the most appropriate measures of action within a specific field of public policies. Sessions within a CA continuously combine small group discussion and plenary discussion with participants

and experts in fields under discussion. It is advisable to distribute the participants in small groups randomly. Plenary debates are usually organised to listen to experts which is then followed by small-group discussion in order to continue advancing on the problem. It is not necessary to reach an agreement at this initial moment; instead, it is about discussing the advantages and disadvantages of the different visions of the experts from the point of view of the participants.

This is followed by a debate on the citizen proposals. The key objective of these discussions would be to find positive and negative justifications of the different measures, as well as the consequences and implications of the application of each one. In the event that the measures were not previously proposed, the justification helps the participants to think about the adequacy of the proposals they prepare.

To broaden participation, the CA participants can also hold open forms in their local area in Tartu, which will help analyse conflicts linked to proposals and generate discussion around them. They can also set up self-managed assemblies to further assist with proposal preparation.

Once this is completed, it is necessary to build recommendations. This is achieved by giving each group measures discussed by another group in the previous step. The task of the group should be to criticise the proposed measures with their appropriate justifications. All criticisms are publicly displayed, helping all the participants to visualise their work from the perspective of other participants. The final dynamic would consist of each small group rethinking their original measurements in light of the criticisms made by the other participants. The final recommendations would be voted on and prioritised at the end of the CA.

Stage 3: Action Plan

Once the CA obtains its results in the form of Recommendations, the question of their implementation arises. The main objective of this phase is to design an action program that defines the tasks that would have to be done to implement a specific recommendation, while establishing the actors that would be involved in its development.

Stage 4: Evaluation and monitoring

This last phase is intended to establish the follow-up system for the proposals of the Assembly and its possible continuity. Two organisations are proposed:

- Follow-up of the proposals: a group of 20 people will be able to have semi-annual meetings with the public administrations in order to know the status of the proposals. The response of the administrations will be mandatory and will be public. One of the tasks of this group is to generate information that can be shared among the population in order to make it easier for citizens to supervise the actions.

- Possibility of calling new debates: 30% of the participants in the CA may propose new debates related to this process and participate in their co-design. Also 20% of the participants in the children's stage can propose new debates.

3. PHOENIX TOOLKIT

This section contains the following tools:

1. Social mapping microsimulation tool, developed by RUG
2. Social Simulation tools on Participatory Behaviour to DI's, developed by RUG
3. Geo-visualization and ecosystem services, developed by UNIFI
4. Self Social mapping, developed by UNIFI
5. Serious e-game: Empaville, developed by SOTON (jointly with OneSource and others partners)
6. Landuse game and social mapping developed by UoI

Each tool is described in a two-pages policy brief. Note that the extended version of the information and elaboration contained in this section can be found in the Deliverable 3.3 *Tangram Portfolio – Part 3 Tools for the Tangram*.

The objective of this section is to allow each partner to cherry pick the tools they want to discuss in detail and use them to create the place-based final Information Package (which will be translated in the local language). This approach recognises that some tools may not be of interest to the local communities, and each implementer will enrich and customise the TCCD Information Package with details that cannot be provided centrally.

This section includes a Toolbox in **Annex 2** (extracted from the Deliverable 3.2), which provides indications and tips for organising a co-design meeting.

3.1 Social mapping microsimulation

Spatial microsimulation is a method of creating an artificial population for small areas, which includes information for variables that are not available from published sources but are important for informing social and area-based policies. Microsimulation models become geographical when spatial information about the simulated entities is available. It involves the creation of large-scale population microdata sets and the analysis of how any policy changes can affect the attributes contained in those microdata sets.

The key benefit of this tool is that it can generate estimates of policy relevant information at different geographical levels (including small area levels). Since there are very few sources of geographically detailed population microdata, there is a need to create these data using spatial microsimulation techniques by merging census and social survey data to simulate a population of individuals within households whose characteristics are as close to the real population as it is possible to estimate. In other words, the models simulate virtual populations in given geographical areas, so that the characteristics of these populations are as close as possible to their “real world” counterparts.

The PHOENIX spatial microsimulation models involve the use of a suitable social survey microdata set, such as the European Social Survey (ESS), including information on relevant demographic and socio-economic characteristics (including age, occupation, social grouping and income) of individuals and households. This survey micro-dataset will be combined with small area information (typically available from sources such as the census of population or administrative data) that paint a picture of the social and economic geography of the pilot regions and also information relating to ‘green’ behaviours and attitudes. Population microdata can be distinguished between individual microdata that contain information on individuals, household microdata which may contain household information only and household microdata which may contain individual and household information. This synthetic population serves as the basis for the next tool – social simulation tools for participatory behaviour.

Spatial microsimulation has been utilised to help paint a picture of how European citizens may feel about issues pertaining to climate change and the European Green Deal. The population is mimicked by drawing on real census data. In each artificial neighbourhood, the structure of the population in its size, density and in social demographics (sex, age, education, employment) is copied to create a digital counterpart. This allows for the analysis of social attitudes at an extremely local level in relation to other individual attributes, such as age group, education level or income, which provides us with a far better and rounded understanding of policy-impact at the micro-level.

In order to measure the success of the tool in terms of modelling performance and accuracy, a key indicator is the extent to which the reconstructed synthetic population matches the official small area tables. This is known as the Total Absolute Error (difference between simulated and actual values). In addition, the success of the tool in terms of sophistication of content is affected by the number of small area tables available for the simulation as well as the number of variables within them. In addition, the success of the tool in terms of geographic granularity is affected by the geographical area at which the small area data are available (the smallest possible area in terms of both population size and geographic area the better).

Figures 3.1 - across Bologna, Iceland, and Gata-Malcata

3.2 Social Simulation tools on Participatory Behaviour to DI's

The social simulation tools were developed to further help us understand how to maximise citizens' participation and how to foster pro-environmental behaviours. The purpose of the model is to stimulate how citizens participate in democratic innovations involving climate change issues. The purpose of the model lies at the heart of the project as the aim is to investigate and further understand how to maximise citizens' participation in DI's and how to foster citizens' adaptation of pro-environmental behaviours. The population is mimicked by drawing on real census data. In each artificial neighbourhood, the structure of the population in its size, density and in social demographics (sex, age, education, employment) is copied to create a digital version. In a nutshell, the social simulation tool consists of an Individual-based model (ABM) that focuses on further understanding citizens participation in DI's by taking socio-cultural, environmental and different administrative levels into account. It conducts an in-depth analysis of evidence-based best-practices (e.g., supporting citizens assemblies, public debate, conferences and public budgeting) for DIs.

The social simulation tool adopts the HUMAT integrated framework which enables it to consider the differences between individuals' demographics (gender, age, education and occupation), what they need and regard as important (attitudes and values regarding climate change), where they live (location and potential neighbourhood effects) and with whom they exchange information (social network). People have different needs, interests and perspectives, are more or less involved in topics, may be more or less susceptible for norms and receptive for information from other people, and their actions may be more or less publicly visible, all of which can affect their attitudes towards a particular topic. A variety of factors influence how individuals might approach the issue of climate change, as they all have their own set of attitudes that determine their motives. These include:

- social needs (belonging to a group of similar others)
- environmental attitudes: (how worried they are about climate change; how much they care for nature and the environment; how often they do things to reduce climate change; whether they favour subsidising renewable energy to reduce climate change; whether they feel the responsibility to do something to reduce climate change).

Individuals differ with respect to the degree to which these needs are important to them, and the degree to which acting on them is satisfying. Furthermore, individuals also have their individual cognitive dissonance tolerance threshold, which if exceeded by the preferred alternative, requires them to take action to reduce it.

This tool thus specifically focuses on processes of attitude formation and information exchange that inform one’s decision to actively participate. In attitude information processes, it simulates how people decide about something considering both their individual needs and social needs. It thus helps simulate what different policy-making authorities can do to implement one policy with the aim of maximising participation. It can produce digital representations of a city, identifying areas where the residing population might have stronger or weaker environmentally friendly values, and can then run a policy intervention to see if and what changes occur. Accordingly, by using the tool, one can simulate the effect of each policy intervention and compare it to a situation in which there are no policy interventions at all.

Figure 3.2 - Bologna ABM Netlogo Interface

3.3 Collective Ecosystems Toolkit

The Collective Ecosystem (ES) toolkit’s first objective is to enhance social learning about environmental issues and inform a dialogue on nature’s value for humans. It serves as a first important step towards a deeper understanding on the interdependence between humanity and natural ecosystems that might increase awareness in terms of individual and collective responsibilities and consequentially, to enhance the understanding of the impact of some specific human behaviours.

This tool is based on the conceptual model proposed by the Intergovernmental Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) which argued that nature should not just be viewed as a commodity to serve human beings. Instead, it provides a more well-rounded view that encompasses nature’s agency and value. Here, the tool employs the concept of Nature’s Contribution to People (NCP) as it recognizes the fundamental role that culture plays in shaping the relationship between humans and nature. By giving importance to the cultural aspects of the relation between nature and societies, it encourages a deeper collaboration between scientists, policymakers, practitioners, and communities that might result in a more fruitful exchange of perspectives from different fields and thus to a more comprehensive and integrated approach to address environmental challenges. Moreover, it aims to foster collective understanding of the impact of some specific human behaviours and support the gradual process of assuming responsibility, as well as promoting better collective recognition of the agency of non-humans.

Figure 3.3 - Mock-up of the dashboard

The toolkit is conceived to support participatory processes dealing with territorial issues. It can be used in different moments of the DI but in any case, it must be understood as an instrument to enhance the participant's knowledge about the interconnectedness between nature and society and more specifically the effect of certain standardised human actions on the environment. Therefore, the tool can be used within a broader participatory process that implicates any kind of territorial transformation.

This toolkit can be used by practitioners at the beginning or during participatory processes or in any moment when it is necessary to collectively reflect and discuss the connection between human societies and nature in general or in relation to a specific choice that might directly or indirectly impact such relation.

3.4 Self Social mapping

The Social Mapping tool is conceived as a digital tool to support public participatory processes around a wide range of territorial issues related to the European Green Deal. It allows citizens to express their opinion, or communicate their knowledge, in a publicly accessible digital platform, and as well as facilitating the creation of community networks around specific issues. Anyone can access the website and explore the menu and the maps, but modifying the maps requires a subscription. Depending on the specific process, users' interaction with the platform may occur by facilitators in an in-person meeting, by home-based users, or both. Once personal information is provided (age, username, password, and email address), users can click on the buttons to modify the maps' content.

It consists of a publicly accessible digital platform aimed at creating local knowledge and engaging local citizens. Firstly, the content uploaded can be used to shape public debates or participatory budgeting. Such content can contribute to highlighting citizens' values and desires, ultimately improving the inclusiveness of the process and the quality of the discussion. Secondly, it can play a role in channelling citizens' interest around local topics and encouraging bottom-up actions in accordance with the process' goal.

The Self Social Mapping platform contains two distinct tools: "Deep map" and "Networking map". They allow citizens to create a digital map of the territory (self-mapping) shared with the public administrations involved in the participatory process (social mapping). The Deep Map aims to gather local knowledge of the territory where the participatory process occurs. Its goal is to create a bottom-up narrative of the territories, thereby fostering self-learning processes among citizens and facilitating interactions between citizens and institutions. Thus, it can be regarded as a valuable tool to give voice to individuals living in the territories and bring out their local narratives. On the other hand, the Networking Map aims to orient territorial action by creating local coalitions of actors. In this way, it can be an important step for encouraging the actual implementation of the strategies outlined in the European Green Deal.

There are five phases of this tool.

- Phase 1 is to present the digital platform to the public. To maximise the tool's success, the preferable option is to take advantage of one of the physical meetings related to the participatory process. The facilitator is required to publicise the website's address and describe its main functions and goals.
- Phase 2 commences with the digital interaction between the users and the platform. This phase can be also carried out in presence. In this case, the facilitator must gather information from the citizens participating in an in-person meeting and then upload them to the website. This option enhances the inclusiveness of the tool, as

people lacking access to the internet or digital skills can more easily participate. Gradually, a deep map containing various types of data will emerge. Data are subdivided into two main categories: Strengths and Criticalities. The former contains the positive aspects of the territory, while the latter contains the negative ones.

- Phase 3 requires an in-presence meeting where the results of the second phase are discussed. The deep map produced may have highlighted a number of issues deemed relevant for the ongoing participatory process. The discussions in a public debate, or in other public meetings related to citizens' participation, could benefit from the consultation of the information uploaded.
- Phases 4 and 5 are optional and are related to labelling information and disseminating it through mailing lists.

For the tool to work best, the participatory process must include moments of public discussions that could take advantage of the information accumulated in the digital platform. This tends to favour processes such as public debates and participatory budgeting. Moreover, given the role played by maps, the participatory process must deal with some type of territorial transformations, being infrastructure developments, urban regenerations, or other projects impacting the area. Lastly, since it is a digital tool, participants must have an internet connection to access the website. In addition, they are required to have an email address and a basic knowledge of digital environments. As a result, the tool might exclude social groups such as the elders and the people without access to an internet connection. To mitigate this issue, it is possible to mediate the interaction with the website by including in-person meetings where a facilitator helps whoever has difficulties in performing these activities.

Figure 3.4 - Social mapping tool mock-up

3.5 Role-playing game Empaville

Empaville is a role-playing game that simulates a Participatory Budgeting process in the imaginary city of Empaville, integrating in-person deliberation with digital voting. The game draws on real Participatory Budgeting experiences and incorporates different elements to provide an educational and critical experience on public participation. In the game, participants engage in discussions and develop project proposals for the city.

During the game, participants are invited to discuss and elaborate on project proposals for the City of Empaville. A democratic process determines a specific portion of the public budget for civic projects after the proposals have been formulated and uploaded on the platform. Participants are required to provide a description for each proposal, indicate its geographical location (neighbourhoods), specify a budget range, and select a category from a predefined list. They engage in group deliberation, upload proposals onto the platform, present them in a plenary session, and vote individually.

The game incorporates conflict generation within and between neighbourhoods to explore how participatory processes can handle conflicts. Participants assume the roles of Empaville citizens, with character cards shaping their profiles and promoting empathy and understanding of diverse perspectives. Each game session is guided by a team of facilitators, typically ranging from 3 to 5 members. The facilitators oversee the deliberative phase and provide digital support, occasionally introducing actions within the group to encourage realistically distorted dynamics that can be analysed during the starting. The cards contain personal data of the characters varying depending on the game versions, shaping the profiles of the participants throughout the gameplay. This setup creates two key role-playing dynamics. At the individual level, participants are motivated to empathise with social actors who possess different personal and social characteristics than their own. This encourages a deeper understanding of diverse perspectives and promotes empathy within the game. At the collective level, the game benefits from a group with varied interests that may potentially conflict. The diverse profiles and characteristics of the participants contribute to realistic and engaging gameplay, allowing for exploration of complex group dynamics.

The Empaville session typically lasts around 90 minutes. Both the traditional Empaville and Green Empaville games follow a structured format consisting of seven phases:

- 1) **Presentation:** the main facilitator introduces the city, its neighbourhoods, and their features. The character cards and game rules are explained, and participants are invited to interpret their assigned character profiles and act in their own interests.

- 2) **Deliberative Tables:** participants are divided into neighbourhood groups to discuss and develop project proposals. Each group can enter their proposals on the platform, providing details such as title, description, location, budget range, category, photos, videos, and attachments. The facilitator encourages participants to initiate the discussion by getting to know each other actively embodying their assigned characters.
- 3) **Proposal Presentation:** representatives from each group briefly present the proposals uploaded on the platform in the plenary. The facilitator coordinates the presentations and ensures time management.
- 4) **Voting Phase:** participants log onto the platform and vote for the proposals. Each participant has three optional votes: two positive and one negative. The vote is personal and based on the character's identity.
- 5) **Winning Ceremony:** after the voting phase ends, the facilitator announces the winning proposal(s). The winning proposals are not necessarily the most voted ones but those that fit within the established budget. The most voted proposal has the 'first right' to the required budget, and subsequent proposals are selected based on the remaining budget, adjusting the voting rank. For this reason, lower budget proposals often have a higher chance of winning. The winning group(s) are rewarded with a symbolic prize, such as a fake check.
- 6) **Data Analysis:** Facilitators and participants analyse the voting data through the platform. The analysis can include total votes, votes for each proposal, percentage of positive and negative votes, votes by gender, neighbourhood, age, and profession. Potential risks and distortions, such as compromising the privacy of individual votes, can also be discussed in this phase.
- 7) **Debriefing:** The session concludes with an open discussion on the overall game process, digital democracy, participatory budgeting, and any other emerging topics raised by the group. In the Green Empaville version, participants engage in discussions on specific environmental issues in addition to those topics.

Empaville serves the purpose of cultivating a culture of public participation and equipping participants with essential tools to understand the benefits and challenges of democratic innovations and the use of technology for participation. Its main objectives are to empower citizens and to encourage their active participation; to foster empathy; encourage collaboration and teach the importance of working together to overcome challenges; and provide insights to policymakers and enable them to better understand the participatory process from a different perspective. It also educates on environmental issues aligned with

the European Union's Green Deal, enhances citizens' skills in conceiving, designing, and developing projects related to the ecological transition and helps raise awareness among citizens and politicians about the social and environmental conflicts that arise in decision-making processes concerning complex environmental issues.

Figure 3.5 – Green Empaville map

3.6 Landsleikurinn – Land Use Game

This tool explores the significance of land use in nature conservation efforts and the potential benefits of utilising interactive online games as a playful platform for citizen engagement in planning green policies.

Land use plays a critical role in determining the health and well-being of ecosystems, as it directly influences habitat availability, species distribution, and ecological connectivity. Unsustainable land use practices contribute to habitat loss, fragmentation, and degradation, posing significant threats to biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. Recognising the importance of sustainable land use is paramount for nature conservation and the overall well-being of our planet. Engaging citizens in decision-making processes related to land use planning and environmental policies is thus essential for fostering a more inclusive and participatory democracy.

However, many individuals feel disconnected from such processes due to complex technicalities and a lack of accessible platforms for meaningful participation. Interactive online games present a unique opportunity to bridge this gap by providing an engaging and accessible means for citizens to interact with or propose land use scenarios that can feed into the development of green policies.

The Land Use Game is a comprehensive, interactive tool that allows users to participate in a simulation of land use decision-making. It provides a platform for users to choose different types of land usage, paint tiles on a map, engage in debates, and share their perspectives on land use. The game is designed to be educational, fostering a better understanding of the complexities involved in land use decisions, and encourages active participation from players.

In a democratic context for planners and policy makers, the Land Use Game offers several benefits. Firstly, it promotes community engagement by involving citizens in the decision-making process and giving them a voice in shaping their community. It allows for a diverse range of perspectives to be considered, leading to more inclusive and representative land use decisions. The game also facilitates dialogue and debate, encouraging players to think critically and consider different viewpoints, which can lead to more informed and thoughtful land use choices.

The game consists of the following phases:

- 1) **Registration** – includes signing up and answering some registration questions related to demographics.
- 2) **Your Land Use Plan** – the player is given instruction on how to use and navigate the map; they click on the icon for the land use they want to propose for an area in the map and then interactively "paint" in the tiles on the map to propose this land use.

- 3) **Survey** – carefully designed to assess and evaluate the correlation between players' choices in the game and their personal values.
- 4) **Review and Debate** – allows players to see all the land use suggestions from all users that have participated in map form and explore all comments that have been made by others.

The Land Use Game offers valuable insights into the potential land use behaviours of different key stakeholders within the research areas. This information helps understand the diverse perspectives and land use preferences of participants. The utilisation of the Land Use Game allows stakeholders with varying backgrounds and interests to actively participate in collaborative discussions, share knowledge, and collectively influence land use decisions by establishing a shared language and framework.

Figure 3.6 – Land Use Game visualisation

4. EVALUATION PLAN

Deliverable 5.2 - *Draft evaluation plan* submitted in July 2022 contained an extensive review of the existing literature on evaluation of participatory/deliberative processes, and a draft plan to co-design the evaluation framework of PHOENIX created by WP5 (Evaluation and Impact Assessment) led by Southampton University (SOTON) based on the grant agreement. This section of the deliverable presents an update on the progress of the co-design process.

The PHOENIX grant agreement required two separate rounds of evaluation. A first round of evaluation exploring the implementation and impact of the Territorial Commission of Co-Design (TCCD) and their ability to enrich existing local participatory and deliberative processes (**TCCD evaluation**, led by University of Coimbra - UC); a second round of evaluation analysing the impact of these Enriched Democratic Innovations on series of specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) listed in the grant agreement itself (**pilot evaluation**, led by SOTON). Consistent with the co-design approach, the PHOENIX project requires to co-design both rounds of evaluation.

Therefore, the evaluation co-design plan is divided in three phases with the objective of sequentially combining different types of knowledges and expertise.

Phase 1: Academic expertise

During the first year of the project, WP5 conducted an extensive and interdisciplinary literature review to identify possible strategies of evaluation and KPIs of interest. This literature review is now published in the open access Handbook of Collective Intelligence⁷ for the part pertaining the evaluation of participatory and deliberative processes.

Phase 2: Internal co-design within the consortium

During the first part of year 2 WP5 conducted extensive co-design both remotely and in the in-person project meetings to create a draft evaluation plan. More specifically, at the Lisbon meeting in June 2022 the initial draft of the evaluation was presented, then the team of SOTON, UC and Res Publica (Task 4.1 - Territorial Commission for Co-Design leader) created

⁷ Spada, P. and Paulson, L., 2023. Measuring the effect of collective intelligence processes that leverage participation and deliberation. In *The Routledge Handbook of Collective Intelligence for Democracy and Governance* (pp. 78-107). Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/oa-edit/10.4324/9781003215929-6/measuring-effect-collective-intelligence-processes-leverage-participation-deliberation-paolo-spada-lex-paulson>

an initial timeline for the implementation and evaluation of the TCCDs that was presented in a videoconference in the fall of 2022. Then during the Paris in person meeting in 2023 the team implemented a co-design process to optimise the draft TCCD evaluation plan. This evaluation plan was then discussed and updated in one-to-one videoconferences in the spring of 2023 and finally approved by all implementers. The process not only generated the co-design plan, but also had important project management impacts. The partners during the year long co-design process highlighted the fact that the original schedule of the PHOENIX project was too optimistic and thus requested an extension.

Phase 3: External Co-design with TCCD members

In the coming months we will ask the TCCD members to collaborate in enriching the evaluation plans and participate in the co-evaluation of both TCCDs and pilots. To preserve comparability, rigour, and efficiency both evaluation plans are designed in a modular fashion. With a core set of KPIs and research strategies that are being designed by the consortium (internal co-design), and extra research strategies and KPIs being identified by TCCD members (external co-design).

At the moment of writing of this document we have completed Phase 2 for the TCCD evaluation plans creating the core evaluation plan, and Phase 1 for the pilot evaluation plan creating a proposal core evaluation plan. Thus, in what follows we present the evaluation plan for the TCCDs that has been vetted and approved by the project Steering Committee and all local partners, and the initial draft of evaluation of the pilots that still requires to complete the internal co-design process that will occur in September. The core module of the TCCD evaluation plan is currently undergoing ethical review (in an advanced phase) and being translated in the local languages to be ready for deployment in the autumn. Instead, the draft pilot evaluation plan will undergo internal co-design in September and subsequently external co-design in the TCCDs. The final evaluation plan of the pilot will be included in the Deliverable 5.5 - *Final modular impact evaluation framework* due in January 2024.

4.1 TCCD evaluation

The evaluation of the TCCDs has been co-designed with the local partners and encompasses both qualitative and quantitative methods. It incorporates five interconnected instruments, working together to offer a comprehensive understanding of the TCCDs implementations. The participatory evaluation approach actively involves TCCD members, encouraging them to share insights and co-evaluate the design process. By incorporating qualitative data and analysis, the evaluation framework is further enhanced, enabling a more effective assessment of the TCCDs activities.

The 5 evaluation instruments are:

1. Qualitative Case Study Description
2. TCCD Qualitative Survey
3. TCCD Internal Evaluation Session
4. Cross-TCCD Online Focus Group
5. Letter of Support

Together, these participatory evaluation instruments contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the TCCD implementations, enhancing the overarching modular evaluation framework. The assessment criteria have been tailored to suit each pilot context, drawing insights from the qualitative findings. The citizen-centred co-evaluation approach aligns perfectly with the project's co-design principles, amplifying community voices and working towards a just, equitable, and sustainable future.

Local partners are requested **to complete data collection by the end of April 2024**, with rolling submissions as instruments are completed.

Qualitative Case Study Description

The Qualitative Case Study provides in-depth and nuanced insights into various forms and processes that TCCDs can undergo. The case studies aim to document and analyse the successes, challenges, and outcomes of the initiatives, along with the mechanisms used to engage participants. The gathered information will contribute to creating a shared knowledge base, identifying best practices by analysing the successes and challenges of different initiatives that can be applied in other contexts.

Each Case Study should adhere to a word count of 500-1000 words, following the provided **template format**, and is expected to be composed of the following parts:

- Part 1 – **TCCD identification and local conditions**

1. **Identification:** Briefly and descriptively introducing the pilot name, region, local partners involved, green deal policy area, type of democratic innovation, and characterisation of the participants.
 2. **Overview:** A concise summary of the process, including its goals, methods, and outcomes.
 3. **Context:** Information on the political, social, and economic context in which the process was developed.
- **Part 2 – The process**
 4. **Methods:** Describing the specific methods and techniques employed to engage citizens in the decision-making process, as well as the criteria used for participant recruitment. This section may also cover any tools or technologies used to support the process and the number of meetings held.
 - **Part 3 – Impacts and lessons learned**
 5. **Outcomes:** Presenting the results and impact of the process, including any changes in policy, decision-making processes, or community dynamics resulting from the TCCD activities. This section may also discuss any unintended consequences or challenges encountered during implementation.
 6. **Analysis:** Providing a critical reflection on the process, drawing insights and lessons learned from the case study. This section may include a discussion of the strengths and weaknesses of the initiative, as well as recommendations for future practice and research.

TCCD Qualitative Survey

The TCCD qualitative survey is designed to capture individual opinions and reflections of TCCD participants regarding their participation. This important self-reflection moment helps gather information to improve the TCCD co-design process. Participants' experiences and insights are critical in this update process, as they share their perspectives on the co-design process, reflect on their roles and contributions, and identify areas for improvement using the SWOT analysis components - Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats.

Structure: The survey is divided into five parts, comprising 26 questions in total. Part A focuses on the co-design process, Part B delves into the TCCD itself, Part C evaluates co-design satisfaction and expectations, Part D explores the relation between the TCCD and the future, and Part E collects socio-demographic information.

Duration: Completing the questionnaire typically takes around 30 minutes.

Application: The survey will be provided via a link and should be administered to all TCCD participants. Local partners may assist in translating the survey, and while online

implementation is preferred, printing the survey and offline completion is possible if needed. In such cases, the completed surveys should be scanned and uploaded to Qualtrics.

After application: Upon completing the data collection, local partners are requested to translate the responses, specifically those related to open-ended questions, into English and provide them to the TCCD evaluation team.

Important Note: The survey should also be applied to those participants who may drop out during this process to understand their reasons and experiences.

TCCD Internal Evaluation Session

The local partners are responsible for conducting a 1.5/2 hour recorded **group discussion with 12-15 diverse TCCD participants**, following the provided **questions**. At the beginning of the session, the facilitator should explain the goal of self-evaluating the co-design process and collect informed consent forms (as the session will be transcribed and translated, recording equipment should be used, and participants should be asked for permission).

For this self-reflection moment, it is essential to create a **safe and supportive environment** where participants feel comfortable sharing their experiences and feedback. Ensuring that everyone has an opportunity to speak and share their thoughts is crucial, while avoiding one participant dominating the conversation.

The facilitator should **actively monitor the discussion**, responding with follow-up questions or comments that encourage further dialogue and keeping the conversation on track and focused on the outlined topics. During the closing of the session, the facilitator should summarise the key insights and learnings in a table, for example, and ask participants to confirm their agreement or suggest any changes.

The Internal Evaluation Session should be **transcribed and translated into English**, using the provided questions to structure the document. Participants need not be identified by name to ensure **anonymisation**; instead, Local Partners may assign each participant an alphabetic letter or other anonymous identifier.

Cross-TCCDs Online Focus Group

Each TCCD should select **one internal representative** to participate in a 2/3-hour collaborative online evaluation discussion. The representative should reflect the diversity of stakeholder perspectives. While fluency in English is recommended for the

representative, it is not mandatory, and **language barriers** can be addressed through possible solutions.

The session will be facilitated by UC and SOTON teams, promoting **knowledge exchange among the PHOENIX TCCDs** and co-creating a SWOT analysis and recommendations. Local partners are requested to support participant selection and documentation of the Internal Evaluation Session findings.

Letter of Support

The Letter of Support – follow up - is designed **to capture the impact of TCCD co-design process** on the life of a participant (or observer). It aims to describe personal and community impacts experienced as a result of the TCCD. Local partners are requested to collect 1-2 participant impact narratives in written letters (translated into English).

Structure: the letter of support should be a written document in the participant language (transcribed to English by the Local Partner), narrating the impact of the TCCD co-design process at a personal (or organisation) level. Each Local Partner will be provided with an example to guide them in crafting the letter. As an option, the letter of support can be accompanied by a short-filmed testimony of the impact of TCCD participation.

Deadline: The deadline for collecting the Letter of Support is 6 months after the co-design process.

4.2 Pilots evaluation:

This section builds upon Deliverable 5.2 - *Draft evaluation plan* and serves as the starting point for the internal co-design process to complete the modular pre/post survey, which will constitute the main instrument of evaluation of each pilot, complemented by a focus group conducted in each pilot. The focus group will aim to enrich and explore the results generated by the surveys and thus will be designed once the survey system is finalised via internal co-design in the fall of 2023. Thus, in what follows we describe the draft pre/post survey system.

4.2.1 participants PRE/POST surveys

Throughout the PHOENIX pilots, WP5 will conduct surveys of participants before the process is initiated and after the process is concluded, or for cyclical/continuous processes, after a significant milestone is achieved. The survey will primarily be deployed online via a **Qualtrics** link, but the option of completing the survey on paper will also be available when necessary to promote inclusion.

The table below presents examples of deployment. The actual deployment will be adapted to each case. Column 2 describes the deployment in the online channel, while Column 3 describes the deployment in the face-to-face channel.

Table 4.2.1 - Examples of Deployment

Time period	Example of Online Channel Deployment	Example of Face-to-Face Channel
T1: During the enrolment in the process [PRE]	The survey can be included as a requirement for the digital enrolment process when using a platform. If the platform is not available, the survey link can be sent via email.	Paper based pre-survey can be deployed during an informational meeting before the start of the process or during the first meeting of the process before the process starts.
T2: After the process is complete (or a critical milestone achieved in the case of continuous processes) [POST]	Post-process email.	Paper based post-survey can be deployed at the end of the last meeting of the process or subsequently.

This approach enables WP5 to assess how the perceptions and attitudes of citizens evolve during the process. The multi-wave approach is common for evaluating Citizens' Assemblies but has seldom been used to study other processes.

When possible, WP5 will not adopt new question wording; instead, we will try to recycle existing questions' wording adopted by the European Social Science Survey or similar international and national surveys. Reusing questions from existing surveys has two advantages. Firstly, these survey questions have been pre-tested and are established measures of the KPIs of interest. Secondly, the questions had been fielded in the same regions in previous years, providing opportunities for comparing the baseline attitudes of participants with the random samples of the wider population (such as comparison of the level of attention to politics). The latter is a critical requirement to achieve an effective open science approach that allows the integration of data with existing research occurring outside the consortium.

Below, we offer a table that describes the draft core set of questions that will be fielded in all pilots, following the requirements of the grant agreement. This is a draft set of questions that contains a superset of KPIs that will be discussed within the consortium during the internal co-design process to achieve an ideal balance between rigour and feasibility.

Based on experience, it is possible to achieve more than 50% coverage of the individual participants using surveys up to 30 questions. Thus, we plan to create a final survey questionnaire that includes 30 questions and set it as a requirement for the implementers to achieve 50% coverage or more.

Table 4.2.2 - Assessing PHOENIX augmented democratic innovations

Dimension	Description	Objectives	Included in PRE	Included in POST
Unique identifier	A unique ID or email	To connect the pre and post survey to track individual level change	YES	YES
Inclusiveness: who participates?	Gender, postal code, age, education, profession, Progressive/Conservative attitudes, Attention to Politics, past voting behaviour, knowledge of the EGD, environmental attitudes	To explore the profile of the participants	YES	NO
Inclusiveness: effective participation	Metrics of effective participation in the process	To explore the participants' perceptions on their ability to participate effectively	NO	YES

Efficacy	Internal & external efficacy metrics	To explore the impact of participating in the process on efficacy indicators	YES	YES
Trust	European, National, and local measures of trust	To explore the impact of participating in the process on trust and anti-politics indicators	YES	YES
Satisfaction with democracy	National and subnational metrics of Democracy Satisfaction	To explore the impact of participating in the process on Democracy satisfaction	YES	YES
Populism, Antipolitics, Scepticism toward experts	Battery of statement designed to capture populist/antipolitics attitudes and scepticism toward experts	To explore the impact of participating in the process on Populism, anti-politics, and Scepticism toward experts' indicators	YES	YES
Readiness to change	Self-reported assessment of willingness to change	To capture the impact of participating in the process on the self-reported willingness to change habit	YES	YES
Perceived process quality	Measures of process quality, legitimacy, and interference from interest groups	To explore the participants' perception of the quality of the process	NO	YES
Learning	Self-reported perception of learning with respect the topic of the pilot and more generally EGD and climate change issues	To Explore the impact of the process on perception of learning	NO	YES

4.2.2 PRE-Survey proposal for internal co-design

In this section, we present a draft of a possible pre-survey instrument to initiate the internal co-design discussion, which needs to be concluded by December 2023.

A few important points to consider:

- a) The **graphics** used here are not representative of the final graphics. The **Qualtrics** account of Southampton University will be used to generate the final questionnaire. Qualtrics is the most widely used professional platform in academia and is mobile-optimised, as most respondents complete surveys on their phone.

- b) Most of the questions are adapted from standard questions that can be found in the **European Social Science Survey** to explore the impact of the participatory process introduced by PHOENIX on the evolution of participant attitudes.
- c) The current survey is presented in English, but the pilot questionnaires will be in **various different languages**. We recommend that the pilot partners find the corresponding question in the European Social Science Survey or in similar national and international questionnaires to optimise translation and understandability for respondents.
- d) The demographics questions will be adapted to reflect national conventions regarding schooling, employment and similar factors. The consortium will then create a recoding scheme to transform locally created data into comparable data. At this stage, we include a standard set of demographics.
- e) Some questions on learning need to be developed locally to target the specific knowledge gains generated by the process.
- f) In this example, we use the email as unique identifier to support the pre/post design, but an anonymous token generated by a digital platform is also a possible substitute.

DEMOGRAPHICS

1. Email account

PLEASE PROVIDE USE WITH AN ACTIVE EMAIL ACCOUNT. WE WILL CONTACT YOU ONLY AFTER THE END OF THE PROJECT TO ASK YOU YOUR FINAL COMMENTS AND EVALUATION.

Email:

2. Gender

PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX

Female

Male

Other

3. Postal code

Postal code:

4. Age
PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX

14 years old or less

Between 15 and 29 years old

Between 30 and 49 years old

Between 50 and 64 years old

65 and over

Don't know/refuse to answer

5. Education (note this will be adapted depending on the pilot nation and schooling system)
PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX

No formal education

Primary School

Secondary School without GCE (part of level 3)

Secondary with GCE (part of level 3 and 4)

Tertiary (level 5 and 6)

Don't know/refuse to answer

6. Profession
PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX

Employed

Unemployed

Retired

Student

LOCAL KNOWLEDGE OF THE ISSUE THAT WILL BE TACKLED IN THE PARTICIPATORY PROCESS

-> **10.** This question will be developed by each local partner in collaboration with the TCCD

EFFICACY

11. How much do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements? PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX IN EACH ROW [This question is adapted from the European Social Science Survey]						
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Don't know
People like me don't have any say in what the [country]'s government does.						
I have a good understanding of the important political issues facing [country].						
I am able to take an active role in a group involved with national political issues						
People like me don't have any say in what the [add the governance level of the participatory process, if the level is national remove the question] government does.						
I am well enough informed to make recommendations on how the [add the governance level of the participatory process, if the level is national remove the question] is governed.						
I am able to take an active role in a group involved with [add the governance level of the participatory process, if the level is national remove the question] political issues						

TRUST

12. On a scale from 0 to 10 how much do you personally trust the following institutions?
Please cross one box in each row [This question is adapted from the European Social Science Survey]

[Country]'s parliament?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
The legal system?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
The police?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Politicians?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Political parties?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
The European Parliament?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
The United Nations?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Scientists?										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Add category 1 targeting elected politicians pertinent to the level of governance of the process created by PHOENIX, for example for a city level participatory process add "[city name]'s council members"										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Add category 2 targeting elected politicians pertinent to the direct potential impact of the process created by PHOENIX, for example for a city level participatory process add "[city name]'s council members supporting the participatory process"										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Add category 3 targeting civil servants pertinent to governance level of the process created by PHOENIX, for example for a city level participatory process add "[city name]'s civil servants"										
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Add category 4 targeting civil servants pertinent to the direct potential impact of the process created by PHOENIX, for example for a city level participatory process add "[city name]'s civil servants"										

SATISFACTION WITH DEMOCRACY

13. Overall, how satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the way democracy works in [Country]? PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX [This question is a standard question appearing in many surveys]

Very dissatisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
A little dissatisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fairly satisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
Very satisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
Don't know/refuse to answer	<input type="checkbox"/>

14. On the whole, how satisfied or dissatisfied are you with the way democracy works [add the governance level of the participatory process, if the level is national remove the question: example "in your city" or "in your region"]?

PLEASE CROSS ONE BOX [This question is a standard question appearing in many surveys]

Very dissatisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
A little dissatisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fairly satisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>
Very satisfied	<input type="checkbox"/>

BATTERY ON POPULISM, (ANTI-)ELITISM, EXPERTISE, AND ANTI-POLITICS

The menu of statements below has been adapted from a recent paper from Oana, and Bojar (2023).⁸ During the internal co-design process, we will refine the battery, isolating the key set of questions that are most relevant for our participatory processes, and (possibly) we may also adapt them to target climate change issues.

Oana and Bojar (2023) preselected the questions with the highest factor loading in the validation of each study, providing a good set of effective questions. However, there are

⁸ Oana, I.E. and Bojar, A., 2023. Populist attitudes, anti-technocratic attitudes, and Covid-related conspiracy beliefs across Europe. *Comparative European Politics*, pp.1-20.

also various other possible question on technocracy that could be included and will be discussed.

[Draft question 15] How much do you agree or disagree with each of the following statements?

Question:	Dimension	Source:
Politicians need to follow the will of the people.	Populism – People centrism	Akkerman et al. (2014)
The people, not the politicians, should make our most important policy decisions.	Populism – People centrism	Akkerman et al. (2014)
I would rather be represented by an ordinary citizen than by a specialized politician.	Populism – People centrism	Akkerman et al. (2014)
I take pride in being an ordinary citizen.	Populism – People centrism	Castanho Silva et al. (2019)
It's important for a political leader to be like the people he or she represents	Populism – People centrism	Castanho Silva et al. (2019)
Politics is ultimately a struggle between good and evil.	Populism – Manichean	Akkerman et al. (2014)
Ordinary citizens don't know what policies are good for them.	Elitism (Inverted to Antielitism)	Bertsou and Caramani (2020)
Political leaders should make decisions according to their best judgment, not the will of the people.	Elitism (Inverted to Antielitism)	Bertsou and Caramani (2020)
The leaders of my country should be more educated and skilled than ordinary citizens.	Expertise (Inverted to Antiexpertise)	Bertsou and Caramani (2020)
The problems facing my country require experts to solve them.	Expertise (Inverted to Antiexpertise)	Bertsou and Caramani (2020)

READINESS TO CHANGE

The university of Florence has developed a comprehensive battery related to Readiness to Change. If the TCCD express interest in using this battery, it can be included as an extra module to the survey. During the internal co-design phase, we will identify a subset of 5 questions from the battery that can be included in the CORE pre and post survey.

The battery needs to be linked to statements about adopting sustainable behaviours that are specific to each participatory process and are co-designed.

The **Readiness to Change for Climate Change scale** consists of 29 items, which are measured by a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The scale captures 7 dimensions: (1) Perceived importance of problem/change; (2) Motivation for change; (3) Self-efficacy; (4) Effectiveness of proposed solution; (5) Social support; (6) Action; (7) Perceived readiness.

[Draft question 16] Please answer the following questions regarding the ADOPTION OF SUSTAINABLE BEHAVIOR. Indicate your degree of agreement from 1 - Strongly Disagree to 5 - Strongly Agree with the following statements about ADOPTING SUSTAINABLE BEHAVIOR.

	1 - Strongly Disagree	2 - Disagree	3 - Neither agree nor disagree	4 - Agree	5 - Strongly Agree
This change is very important for me					
At this point I feel the need to change					
I think it is appropriate to change my behavior					
My life would be worse if I didn't change					
I am determined to change my habits					
I feel motivated to undertake this path of change					
I have many reasons to change					
I want to change this aspect of my life					
I am confident in my ability to change habits					

I feel capable of overcoming any challenge related to my change					
I will be able to stay true to my new routine					
If I am going to have a setback, I am confident that I will be able to overcome it					
I think I have the resources to make this change					
I think there are effective ways of dealing with this change					
I have faith in the paths proposed to support my change					
I am aware of strategies / techniques / methods that could help me change					
I think what was proposed to me might work					
I feel supported by the people close to me in this change					
I think my community would help me on this path					
The people around me would approve of my change					
I know who to turn to among the people close to me for help in changing					
I am already doing something to solve my problem					
Sometimes I try to find solutions that can work					
I changed my behaviors to fix the problem					
I started my journey to try to do something					
I am ready to change					
I think I'm ready to change my habits					
I believe I am ready to tackle the problem					
In all honesty, I don't feel like I'm ready to really change my life					

4.2.3 POST-Survey proposal for internal co-design

As indicated in the table below, the post-survey will not include demographics and, instead, will include three key metrics: 1. Effective Participation, 2. Perceived Process Quality, and 3. Learning.

Table 4.2.3 - Differences between pre and post surveys

Dimension	Description	Objectives	Included in PRE	Included in POST
Inclusiveness: who participates?	Gender, postal code, age, education, profession, Progressive/Conservative attitudes, Attention to Politics, past voting behaviour, knowledge of the EGD, environmental attitudes	To explore the profile of the participants	YES	NO
Inclusiveness: effective participation	Metrics of effective participation in the process	To explore the participants' perceptions on their ability to participate effectively	NO	YES
Perceived process quality	Measures of process quality, legitimacy, and interference from interest groups	To explore the participants' perception of the quality of the process	NO	YES
Learning	Self-reported perception of learning with respect the topic of the pilot and more generally EGD and climate change issues	To Explore the impact of the process on perception of learning	NO	YES

INCLUSIVENESS: EFFECTIVE PARTICIPATION

To assess the effective inclusiveness of the process, we have adapted the battery of questions developed by the OECD to evaluate the effective inclusiveness of members of minipublics. The battery of question below represents a superset from which the PHOENIX consortium will select the final battery of questions. The OECD battery we have selected is a generalist one that applies to any type of participatory and deliberative process. During the co-design process, the consortium might add extra KPIs that are process-specific. For

example, for processes that make us of moderators, the consortium might add questions relating the quality of the moderators' activities.

→ **How many of the other members did you feel had different views compared to your own?**

1. None
2. A few of them
3. About half of them
4. Most of them
5. I don't know

→ **Did you feel there were any groups or parts of society that were not represented on this panel?**

1. Yes
2. No

→ **If you feel any groups or parts of society were not represented, which group or groups did you feel was/were missing?**

→ **Were there any obstacles that made it difficult for you to attend the sessions?**

1. Yes
2. No

→ **If there were obstacles that made it difficult for you to attend, what were they? Tick all that apply. [randomised response order for options a-e]**

1. Barriers related to my personal life (for example, family commitments)
2. Barriers related to my work (for example, irregular working hours, or busy schedule)
3. Financial barriers (for example, travelling costs)
4. The time this process demands
5. Yes, other barriers (please specify _____)
6. I don't know

→ **Do you have any suggestions of what could be done to improve the ability for anyone to attend such a process?**

→ **Please answer all the following questions on a scale of 0 to 10, where 0 means “not at all” and 10 means “to a great extent”. To what extent, if at all, do you feel that:**

1. You had a fair number of opportunities to speak
2. Other members had a fair number of opportunities to speak
3. All members were heard equally
4. No members dominated the discussions
5. You and your views were heard

PERCEIVED PROCESS QUALITY AND SATISFACTION WITH THE PROCESS

Most questions regarding the process quality are process-specific and will be developed in collaboration with the local implementers based on the process they will co-design with the TCCD.

The following are some general questions regarding the perceived level of satisfaction. These questions are derived from the Participedia evaluation questionnaire.

→ **In general, how satisfied are you with the process as a whole?**

1. Very dissatisfied
2. Dissatisfied
3. Somewhat dissatisfied
4. Neutral
5. Somewhat satisfied
6. Satisfied
7. Very satisfied

→ **In general, how satisfied are you with the outcomes of the process?**

1. Very dissatisfied
2. Dissatisfied
3. Somewhat dissatisfied
4. Neutral
5. Somewhat satisfied
6. Satisfied
7. Very satisfied

LEARNING

Learning will be assessed by including a set of factual questions about the climate issue that participants engaged with. These factual questions will be included in the pre and post survey to observe changes in the number of correct answers. The local partner, in collaboration with the TCCD, will be responsible for developing the factual questions that are relevant to the specific interests of the TCCD.

In addition to factual learning, the post-survey will also include a self-reported assessment of perceived individual learning. The following is the version of this assessment offered by the OECD evaluation approach for minipublics:

→ **Please answer all the following questions on a scale of 0 to 10, where 0 means “not at all” and 10 means “to a great extent”. To what extent, if at all, do you feel that:**

1. Your understanding of the issue became clearer throughout the process
2. You gained more arguments and perspectives to support your own opinion about the issue
3. You understood the arguments, perspectives, and concerns of others
4. Your understanding of others’ opinions of the issue became clearer through this process
5. On a scale of 0 to 10, where 0 means “not at all informed” and 10 means “very well informed”, to what extent, if at all, do you feel that you are informed at the moment on the following issues: **[include a list of issues relevant to the key policy issue addressed]**

Conclusion

The modular structure of this deliverable empowers each implementer to craft a customised Information Package for their specific Territorial Commission of Co-Design, providing a comprehensive understanding of the PHOENIX principles, methodology, tools, and tangrams proposed for the pilot territories.

Throughout the contents of this deliverable, we have addressed significant aspects of the PHOENIX project. By democratising the project's findings, goals, and means, our aim is to create a shared knowledge base that fosters a deeper understanding of participatory processes, both within and beyond the TCCDs.

The essence of the PHOENIX project lies in its commitment to co-design. This approach represents a significant innovation towards effective and inclusive participatory processes. By actively engaging citizens and stakeholders, we empower individuals to shape the collective future of their communities. The TCCDs serve as a powerful demonstration of how co-design can democratise decision-making and promote civic engagement. As we witness the integration of co-design in participatory processes, we anticipate a transformative impact on democracy, enriching the foundation of democratic innovations. Our collective effort and hope are aimed at fostering a more inclusive and empowered democracy, ensuring a just, equitable, and sustainable future for all.

In conclusion, the PHOENIX project's dedication to co-design marks a significant milestone in redefining the conception and design of democratic practices. Through the TCCDs, we are paving the way for a more inclusive and empowered democracy. The journey has just begun, and we are eager to witness the positive change that this participatory approach will bring to the communities and territories involved. As we move forward, we remain committed to fostering effective and sustainable democratic innovations that strengthen the bond between citizens and governance, ensuring a more just, equitable, and sustainable future for all.

Annex 1: An example of TCCD Information Package index

1. Introduction

The introduction describes the objective of the TCCD, its composition, number of meetings, and activities. If desired, Section 1.1 can include a general introduction to what co-design means, written for a general audience⁹. Section 1.2 provides a general guide about the variety of TCCD activities that are considered core or ancillary, which can serve as inspiration. The introduction should emphasise that the Information Package should be considered a starting point to initiate (or continue) discussion and not an end point. From a style perspective, it is important that the information provided is not prescriptive but reflects the overall objective of PHOENIX to promote open co-design.

2. Pilot implementation co-design activities: description & information

The key objective of the TCCD, according to the guide in section 1.2, is to co-design and enrich the proposed tangram generated by the project, and if possible, monitor the execution of the pilot. The Information Package should describe the plan of this co-design process and include the information necessary to start/continue it. [Annex 2](#) offers a model for a co-design meeting description. Sections 2 and 3 contain the assets that can be used to discuss the local proposed tangram, tools that might be used to begin the discussion, and possibly reflections on tools that cannot be used in the PHOENIX pilot but could be interesting to include in the future. As explained by the guide, this is the most important TCCD activity, and multiple meetings should be dedicated to it.

3. Pilot evaluation co-design activities: description & information

The TCCD can decide to enrich the core evaluation of the pilot mandated by the grant agreement. In order to enable this process, the Information Package should describe an activity to review the evaluation framework of the pilot and propose extra KPIs to be included in the pre/post survey for the participants, or eventually extra research data collection strategies that might be of interest (such as a survey to civil servants). Section 4.2 contains the draft pre/post survey that includes the core set of questions that all pilot participants will have to answer. To this set, extra questions can be added. The core pre/post survey will be finalised via an internal co-design process that will be completed by the end of September 2023. Then the TCCDs have time until December 2023 to propose extra KPIs so that the final completed survey will be ready for the start

⁹ See Section 1.2 of this deliverable.

of the pilots. It is important to manage the expectations of participants considering the ability of each implementer and academic partner to conduct extra research. It is also important to manage the integrity of the core research mandated by the grant agreement, which is designed to generate a comparable impact evaluation framework. Operationally, we do not recommend entering into technical question revision or creation due to the difficulties of the process and the time required to train participants in writing rigorous questions. Instead, we recommend that each implementer discusses with TCCD members general research ideas and KPIs, which are then transmitted back to the academic team for operationalisation.

4. Description of the TCCD self-evaluation and reflection activity

The TCCD will evaluate itself using a survey, a dedicated feedback session, and a cross-TCCD discussion, as planned and co-designed by the project consortium (as described in Section 4.1 of this deliverable). Thus, we recommend that these self-evaluation activities are described in the Information Package.

5. Conclusion

We recommend that the conclusion highlights that The TCCD is the most important and innovative aspect of the PHOENIX project and that the Information Package is designed as a starting point to enable an impactful and reasoned activity of each TCCD. It is not designed to be a comprehensive and final set of information needed to conduct co-design; thus, the participants themselves are invited to request the implementers to provide extra information that might be locally relevant.

Annex 2: Toolbox (from Deliverable 3.2)

1. Organization and Design of Participatory Workshops¹⁰.

Approaching the practical way of carrying out the participatory workshops, it is convenient to insist on numerous aspects that together are those that make possible the success in the fulfilment of its objectives. We will treat them based on two fundamental stages, such as the previous preparation and the realization of the workshop.

Preparation of the participatory workshop.

The first task that we must consider when we program the realization of a participatory workshop will be to define the objectives and the results that we intend to achieve. These two elements will guide us later to think about the techniques that we will use, the duration of the workshop and its parts, and all the aspects that will characterize each workshop (materials, functions of the technicians, characteristics of the space, etc.). Here are some elements that we must take into account and that will help us define the workshop:

- It is advisable that the duration of the workshop does not exceed 2 hours. It is very difficult to keep the attention of the participants for a longer time, and in less time, it is almost impossible to go through the different moments that a workshop requires. If we work with people used to working in groups, it is possible to extend the workshops for longer, but it is advisable to take breaks in order to maintain attention.
- The participants in the workshops have to know from the beginning what is going to be done.
- Different internal phases must be organized in the workshop with stipulated times. The workshops can be carried out in several sessions.
- There are countless techniques available to use in workshops, the important thing is that we choose the most appropriate based on the objectives that we have set ourselves, and that we make the necessary adaptations. We can even create or adapt specific techniques for the specific case being treated.

To define the technique to be used, we must first answer the following questions:

- WHAT topic are we going to address?
- WHY did we carry out the workshop (objective)?

¹⁰ (Source: Democracy in action: Participatory Methodologies in <https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/79311/1/400543.pdf>)

- WITH WHOM are you going to work (profile of participants)?

When defining the technique to use, we must feel safe to conduct it. When we resort to techniques that we have not previously used, it is advisable to carry out simulations before the workshop, which allow us to approach them later in an agile and comfortable way. Once the technique has been chosen, we must specify the procedure to follow for its application depending on the expected number of participants, the time and space available.

While not everything is predictable, we must be prepared to reconsider the development of the workshop if necessary (because more or fewer people have attended than expected, because it is necessary to motivate people first, because we do not have the necessary time, etc.) It is advisable to have a “plan B”, with other backup techniques that fit the scenario we find ourselves with.

In the event that we use more than one technique in the same workshop, the link between one and the other must be clear to the participants, in such a way that progress is made in an orderly and systematic process.

The simpler the technique, the better. It is important that the techniques are "manageable" in such a way that the participants can gradually incorporate them (transfer of social technology) thus promoting the establishment of "other ways of doing" after the process.

The space where the workshop is going to be held is more important than what is generally granted a priori. A comfortable and accessible space does not guarantee the success of a workshop, but it greatly favours the work climate.

Whenever a workshop is done, it has to end with a visualizable result for the participants, regardless of whether we have divided the workshop into several sessions. It is important that in each document that is prepared in the workshops, the date on which it was carried out and who participated is recorded. At the end of the workshop it is advisable to evaluate the meeting with some simple technique.

Realization of the participatory workshop

Below we generically show the different important aspects of conducting a workshop. It is evidently a moment of interaction between the technicians who direct it methodologically and the participants who lead it with respect to their dialogue and contributions. The fundamental elements that we must take into account when conducting a workshop are:

- Always start from practice, from what people know, experience and feel.
- Develop a systematization process of this practice, an orderly, progressive process and at the pace of the participants, which allows for the discovery of new elements and to go deeper according to the level of progress of the group; to locate the daily,

the immediate, the individual and partial, within the social, the collective, the historical, the structural.

- This process must provide new elements that allow the initial knowledge, the feeling from which we start, to be fully explained and understood. Based on these elements, a workshop can be carried out in multiple ways, as long as the objective is to facilitate dialogue and reflection among all.

Key aspects and moments are:

1. Presentation. At the beginning of the workshop we have to show what is going to be done in the workshop, what is to be achieved with it, what techniques are going to be used and at what times. The meaning of the workshop within the process must also be clear, that is, the workspace that is being opened has an objective in itself, but at the same time it constitutes a moment within a whole process that gives it meaning: it is You arrive at the workshop after having carried out a series of activities (meetings, other workshops, interviews, etc.) and other work spaces will continue to open after the workshop. The clearer the meaning and continuity of the workshop in the future, the easier the work will be and, usually, the greater involvement on the part of the attendees.

Waiting while the session begins can be used to introduce yourself and others.

2. First reflection: division into small groups. Once what is going to be done has been explained and it is clear to the participants, we begin the workshop. The dynamics of a workshop have to be well thought out by the technicians; In order to be creative and adapt to circumstances, it is necessary to know in advance what you want to do. Whenever the number of attendees is greater than 10 or 15 people, it is advisable to divide into small groups in order to facilitate dialogue and reflection on the content of the workshop. In some cases (depending on the objectives) we will form homogeneous groups, while in others it will be more appropriate to work with heterogeneous groups. The division can be done randomly, according to the preferences of the participants or by any method that allows us to generate the type of group expected. We must bear in mind that when we arrive at a meeting we usually sit next to the people we know, so homogeneous groups are usually already formed naturally. Each of the small groups always has to choose a rapporteur who will later show the rest of the groups the work done. This work in groups guarantees a more direct debate to agree proposals or opinions on the aspects that are dealt with.

3. Second reflection: plenary. In the event that division by groups is used, finally all the attendees must be brought together in a plenary session in which each group recounts what they have discussed and decided. At this point it is very important that there is a large support on which to write down everything that each group says. The support makes it possible to make the problem publicly visible, in short, it makes it easier for each group to see their own reflections on said support and, at the end of the process, to be able to have a plural and heterogeneous relationship of the same problem. The most advisable thing is that the support is identical to the one used by the small groups in their reflections. If a division into small groups has not been carried out, what we have called the first and second reflection merge at the same moment, collecting the same characteristics. It should be clarified that this process of division, work in sub-groups and meeting in plenary does not have to be carried out only once, but can be carried out as many times as deemed necessary until it matures and clearly defines the results sought with each workshop.
4. Conclusions: when we do a workshop it is recommended that it always end with a result or conclusions. These will always come from the previous exercises and have to leave open a door to the future, that is, to its continuation, either in another session of the workshop, or because we have finished the diagnosis and entered another phase. With the development of the workshop itself, it can go to different sites depending on the objectives pursued. You can open a debate on what has been reflected. When opening it, it is advisable that it have a result as its horizon (we want to reach an agreement, an alternative or a definition), since it will be this objective that will allow us to have a transparent and horizontal debate between those involved., as well as delimiting the debate itself, avoiding its excessive prolongation. Based on the reflections made previously, the objective may be to group the elements that are similar and treat the different ones, discuss the prioritization of said elements, consolidate consensus. In any of these cases, depending on the workshop in which we find ourselves and depending on the moment of the participatory process, the completion must be linked to the next action (workshop or other activity), which will begin by compiling what was worked on in the previous workshop. On these occasions it is convenient to send the product of the previous work in advance, so that if new participants are incorporated, they can all have the same inputs. The role of the technicians in the workshop is a very important issue since the proper development of the workshop can depend on them. It must be taken into account that through the methodologies.

In participative organizations, we do not want to position ourselves as expert technicians in the subject being addressed, but rather as technicians who think that reaching collective and public solutions requires a methodological process of which we are supporters. This thematic neutrality is important, because it makes it easier for the technician to address other issues more related to the development of the workshop. Our purpose is not to assess and judge the comments of the participants but to create the right environment for them to argue their ideas or appreciations. In this sense, the technician is a kind of connector who, when faced with a new idea, claims his argument, and takes it to public display so that the rest of the participants can listen and reflect on it. The technician becomes a facilitator who is clear that the objective is to reach joint alternatives. Those who have to assess the viability of one idea, or another are precisely the participants. In this way, we can say that the technicians have to assume different roles that guarantee the proper functioning of the workshop:

- a. Make the participation and contribution of all possible. Supervising that speaking turns are distributed among all, as well as the work in groups; You must look for techniques that guarantee equal conditions for these dialogues (card system, balancing the right to intervene, distributing the groups, etc.).

BE CAREFUL THAT:

- No person is restricted by having to speak in public.
- No opinion or comment is left unheard
- All people are represented in the result

- b. You can introduce elements to invigorate the discussion or to open new lines of debate. Whether from the review of secondary data or from workshops and other techniques that have been applied previously, issues may have emerged that are considered relevant and yet do not appear in the current workshop. The technician can introduce them in order to open a line of discussion while he can constitute a latent element, or simply in order to verify that it does not constitute a problem that is given the same relevance among one and other actors.
- c. It must have a clear objective of promoting this dialogue, discussion and collective decision-making. Stimulating creativity, improvising from the material that emerges from the techniques, giving names to the different groups of ideas, etc., must channel through the promotion of collective decision the multiple ideas and interpretations that come out.

2. SOCIAL MAPS¹¹

The sociogram is a technique that we use within the participatory methodologies for the analysis of social networks. Its objective is to generate knowledge about the structure of the networks in a specific territory and open processes of reflection on them, defining collective strategies to unblock conflicts and move forward. We can understand this technique of the sociogram as an x-ray (or still photo) of the relationships that are established between different actors in front of a certain topic, at a given moment. It allows us to graphically represent these relationships, situate the actors facing a certain issue and/or problem, as well as on the social map, taking into account the degree of power they have in relation to the analysed problem.

The sociogram can be used at different times and with different objectives within a participatory process.

1. To know, at the beginning of a process, the map of relationships that are established around a problem at a certain moment. It then constitutes an essential tool for the contextualization of the social actors in front of an issue.
2. As a working hypothesis for carrying out the positional sample of the different actors in the territory, that is, to distinguish which actors there are, what relationships they have among themselves, and who are closer or farther from our objective.
3. To see the movement of the actors and/or networks facing a specific problem. By making successive sociograms in the course of a participatory process, we can visualize this movement, as well as the articulations that occur between the networks, connection points, agreements, points of conflict, etc.
4. To prepare the Action Plan once the diagnosis has been made. Network analysis is a fundamental element at the time of programming as it allows us to define strategies (with whom we should negotiate, which alliances we start from and which ones we should promote, what conflicts exist between the actors and/or networks) in order to give viability and sustainability of the actions.

The workshop that we will develop next refers to the analysis of networks in the diagnosis-contextualization¹¹ stage; its objective is therefore more descriptive than mobilizing. The analysis of the SOCIAL MAP will give us as a result a contextualization of the social network of relationships around a specific problem.

¹¹ Source: Democracy in action: Participatory Methodologies in <https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/79311/1/400543.pdf>

The third variable that we introduce is the links that are established between some actors and others. We graph these links not based on the relationships they have between them in a generic way, but focusing specifically on the specific issue on which we are working, and at the present time. To graph the relationships between the actors, it is usual to use the following symbols:

Another important element is to know if the relationships are reciprocal or one-way, for this we graph with one-way or double-way arrows.

The conventions we have described are the ones we normally use in our work, but these can be defined and agreed with the group you are working with; The important thing is that they are used at the different moments in which the maps are worked on so that we all know what each of them symbolizes and we can make comparative readings. It is also important to put the date and place where the social map was made, as well as the authors of it.

First reflection

The first step to follow is to prepare a list of actors that the participants locate in the territory, linked to the theme that we are addressing and determine the symbology that corresponds to each one (triangles, squares or circles).

This first step must be worked on in plenary so that the groups start from the same list of actors in their graph. We can approach it through a brainstorming session (10 minutes) so that the participants define which actors in the territory they know that can be related to the problem being addressed at the present time. The facilitator writes down on the support or blackboard the actors that are being identified. In case there are relevant actors who are being left out, the facilitator can introduce the debate through questions in order to analyse the relevance or not of considering them. At the end, there would be a list of actors agreed upon by the participants, and the symbology corresponding to each actor would be determined. This first step would last approximately 45 minutes.

Once we have the list of actors with the corresponding symbols, we ask the participants to divide into heterogeneous groups and name a rapporteur who will be the person who will present the results of their group's work to the plenary. In this first reflection, the groups will work on:

1. Locate the actors on the map, taking into account, on the one hand, their degree of power or influence with respect to the subject or problem being dealt with, and on the other, their affinity with respect to the objectives pursued.
2. Determine the relationships (links) that are established between the actors (whether they are strong, weak, normal, conflictive relationships). It is important at this point that the technician makes it very clear that the relationships that interest us are not those that are established in a generic way between the different actors / networks, but specifically those that are established around the specific topic that is being addressed. Two actors may not have a very fluid relationship on a daily basis and, nevertheless, it may be that around the particular issue at hand, they articulate a series of very specific and delimited relationships. The opposite situation can also occur: that two or more actors habitually maintain fluid relations and yet do not

have any link between them, nor activities in common in relation to the subject that we are addressing.

For the development of this first reflection, an approximate time of 60 minutes would be given.

Second reflection

Once the groups have finished the entrusted task, they return to the plenary and each rapporteur of the group makes the presentation of the results of the work carried out. In this type of workshop, time should be given after the presentation of the different groups to discuss the elements that may appear contradictory in the graphing of the map, in order to try to reach a consensus. If it is not achieved in a prudent time, the differences should be raised in order to settle them in a later session, in which there will surely be more knowledge of the network framework and their relationships. The approximate duration of the presentation and the debate in plenary will be between 60 and 90 minutes, depending on the number of groups that must present and the time required to reach a consensus on the map.

If the number of participants is not so high as to work in plenary (up to 15 or 20 people), we can divide them into groups so that they locate the actors in the matrix and hold the plenary in order to debate and agree on a single matrix. to then work on the relationships that exist between the actors present in said matrix.

Conclusions

Once the stakeholder map is agreed upon, we must read both the process we have carried out to reach the final result, as well as the product obtained and what it is telling us in relation to the subject on which we are working. This reading will be guided by the objective that we set ourselves when planning the workshop (have a first mapping of actors, prepare the sample, define strategies to expand sets of action, analyse the movements that have occurred in the networks by comparing it with a previous mapping, etc.)

While we have focused the explanation of the technique to use it in the diagnosis-contextualization stage, we point out some of the elements to take into account at this specific moment in the process:

- Highlight whether there were generalized agreements or contradictions regarding the location and/or relationships of some of the actors. In the event that a consensus has not been reached for the location and/or type of relationships of some of the actors, explain that as the field work progresses, it will be possible to clarify its position.

- Highlight (if they appear) the existence of empty quadrants and/or actors for whom no type of relationship has been established, linking them more to a current ignorance of the participants of this type of actor than to the real absence of the same.
- Highlight whether or not the technical team has been located in the matrix as one more actor in the process, in which quadrant and with what relationships.
- Analyse whether there is an agglomeration of actors and relationships in certain rows or columns of the matrix, linking it with the profile of the participants and with the knowledge/unknowledge that it implies. For example, in the sociograms that are carried out with administration technicians, it often happens that we find a complex network of actors and relationships in the middle row, with a smaller number of actors and relationships in the upper part and, above all, with very few actors in the lower part, or with a diffuse identification of them that corresponds more to the categories of "groups" (men, women, children,...) with which they work than with an identification of "groups" or "informal networks. If, on the contrary, the participants are members of informal groups, it is much more probable that the resulting sociogram will be very "loaded" with actors and relationships below, and that they will gradually become poorer in the upper ranks.

ACTION PLAN¹².

Once the CA obtains its results in the form of Recommendations, the question of their implementation arises. This phase requires the participation of all TCCD members. It involves putting recommendations into action by designing an action plan that defines the means by which a recommendation will be executed. The main objective of this phase is to design an action program that adequately defines the tasks that would have to be done to implement a specific recommendation, while establishing the actors that would be involved in its development. The phase can be carried out by all the members of the TCCD.

In either case, what is sought with the Action Plan is to discuss how the recommendations made can be implemented and what is necessary and who should be engaged to do so. The description of the environment and the actors involved in this work allows the establishment of indicators capable of facilitating the monitoring of the execution of the recommendations elaborated in the participatory process.

1. Defining the objectives and purpose of the recommendations.

¹² Source: Democracy in action: Participatory Methodologies in <https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/79311/1/400543.pdf>

Here it would be a matter of collecting the recommendations that come from the participatory process and beginning to think about them in operational terms. All the recommendations can be broken down into one or several proposals. Maybe not. The case is to encourage participants to disaggregate the recommendations and associate each proposal with a purpose or objective. This exercise will be very useful for later designing concrete activities to implement each recommendation.

How to build links between professional knowledge and citizen knowledge in a systemic approach? Between external knowledge, detailed information on climate change and biodiversity, and personal testimonies and stories? Once DIs are implemented, citizens can develop their conversation in a frame previously defined by experts; they can co-produce the frame, or even develop a counter-expertise. But we also insist on the need to show experts in disagreement, as it is important to make it clear that there are different positions and perspectives even on the expert side. There is a consensus in the scientific field about the reality of global warming, so that, on this issue, but there are huge differences among experts about how to face this threat: on the balance prevention/adaptation, on the binding vs. incentive measures, on the social groups that have to make more efforts than others, on the countries that have to make more efforts than others, there are important dissensus.

It is also important to reflect on the place to be left or not to climate scepticism, among participants and stakeholders: should the European epistemic framework given by the Green Deal be discussed? Generally speaking, how can we think about the framing of problems? What relationship should be built between "democratic truth" and "scientific truth"? The theory of epistemic democracy does not solve per se the relation between citizens' knowledge and experts' knowledge.

Recommendation 1	
Proposals	Ends and objectives
Proposal 1	
Proposal 2	
Proposal...	

2. Defining the activities and the actors involved

Once we have disaggregated the recommendations into more operational proposals, it is now a matter of reflecting on the activities that we think are appropriate to carry them out. These activities will in turn be associated with both actors, who will have a specific responsibility in their development.

Recommendation 1					
Proposals	Activities	Actor 1	Actor 2	Actor 3	Other actors
1.	1.1				
	1.2				
	1...				
2.	2.1				
	2.2				
	2...				

From here, a Commission can be designed within the TCCD to supervise the implementation of the recommendations. But this phase also makes it possible to generate information that can be shared among the population in order to make it easier for citizens to supervise the actions.